

REPUTATION MECHANICS, DIGITAL CURRENCY MODEL AND NETWORK DYNAMICS AND ALGORITHMS

D3.2

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This document presents the outcomes of the work carried out through Work Package 3 of the PIE News project. It describes the conceptual and empirical context for research and development around components/systems for commonfare.net relating to digital currency, social dynamics and systems facilitating trust and recognizing constructive contributions to the commonfare. It also presents practical suggestions for such components/systems.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fig. 02

This document presents the final suggestions and recommendations arising from WP3.

WP3's remit included desk-top and empirical research and development work towards the creation of components/systems on the commonfare.net platform that would:

- ▶ Allow for the implementation of complementary, digital currencies in the form of cryptographically-secured digital exchange tokens;
- ▶ Facilitate information diffusion;
- ▶ Facilitate the formation of trusting relationships; and hence;
- ▶ Contribute to the long-term sustainability and growth of the platform, and so to the creation or facilitation of a commonfare approach to welfare provision in Europe.

In chapter 2, we present an overview of the commonfare concept and the possibilities for the platform. We also present a novel conceptualization of the platform as an assemblage of users (commoners) and digital objects or resources (such as stories and profiles) which underpins the development of many of the ideas subsequently presented in Chapter 4.

In Chapter 3, we summarize the results of earlier empirical research, already published in D2.1 and D3.1 of particular relevance to WP3. We also present new findings from subsequent work. We note that key issues of relevance to WP3 include:

- ▶ A widespread desire to feel part of a community with shared values, especially one which cooperates and acts in a mutualistic way to increase the quality of life of the many.
- ▶ Widespread concern over privacy and data control issues, and a concomitant mistrust of technical corporations and platforms such as Google and Facebook.

▶ New forms of rather fragmented solidarity that may result in overly-segregated group formation and hence obstacles to the diffusion of knowledge and good practice.

▶ A strong desire for self-determination, autonomy, and freedom from conditionalities imposed by the State, non-governmental authorities such as NGOs, and capitalist entities such as employers and big businesses.

▶ A perception that trust in the platform would be as or even more important than trust in the individuals a commoner might potentially interact with.

▶ The increasing prevalence and hidden impact of personal indebtedness.

▶ Willingness to experiment with complementary (digital) currencies.

▶ Interest in currency systems that include an unconditional basic income, and that exclude loans at interest and speculation.

▶ Ambivalence or contradictory views about whether contributions to the common good should be rewarded, but a general desire that they should be recognized and visible to others.

These findings have important implications for the design of the platform, including but not limited to the components/systems described in Chapter 4.

Chapter 4 presents concrete proposals for components/systems on the commonfare.net platform within the remit of WP3.

Section 4.1 puts forward three alternatives for implementing one or more digital currencies in the form of cryptographically-secured digital exchange tokens.

The first of these options is a currency system based on the digital currency for the cooperative movement, Faircoin2. We note that Faircoin aligns well with the commonfare

project in terms of ethics and ethos, but that it has some potential disadvantages relating to scalability and hence long-term sustainability of the platform, especially beyond the life of the formal PIE News project.

The second option considered is use of the Yetta Protocol and associated smart contracts, and the use of the Yetta Token in the platform. This has the advantage of good potential for scalability and long-term sustainability, because it introduces a mechanism for the influx of additional financial capital into commonfare.net (and hence to the community of commoners) on a long-term, continuous basis. However it does so on the basis of prosocial spending and philanthropic investment, something which could bring its own risks for platform sustainability. For example, if the expected returns are not high, this could dis-incentivize further investments into the system, something which the project partners and platform would have no control over.

The third option presented in Section 4.1 is a dual complementary currency system introducing both the Yetta Token (as described in the second option) and a site-specific coin. This site-specific coin would have the advantages of being closed, autonomous and independent, and could function as an exchange token within the commoner community. However, it would not provide much advantage in terms of actual debt relief or income generation for use in non-commonfare.net related contexts – hence the suggestion of maintaining a parallel currency system using the Yetta Token.

Section 4.2 describes ways of integrating network dynamics analysis and systems for the facilitation of trust, the recognition of constructive contributions towards the commonfare, and detection of (and subsequent action on)

platform misuse. Building on the notion of commonfare.net as an assemblage described in Chapter 2, we propose using network dynamics metrics to calculate the contribution individual actants in the network (both commoners and digital resources) make to the strength of the commonfare in any given period. We propose calling the aggregate contribution of a commoner and the digital resources she owns her commonshare. We then make a series of suggestions for how the commonshare value might be used to enhance the strength, growth and sustainability of the platform. We also suggest supplementary components or features that might be needed to help commoners decide with whom they wish to interact or establish trusting relations.

Because this is a novel approach, we strongly suggest that it first be trialled through experiments on the platform's trace data carried out in the background, with no representation or visibility on the platform interface. We also note that final decisions regarding some of the norms and rules on the platform should be negotiated within the commoner community, rather than imposed from the level of the project consortium. To this end, we urge more participatory co-design work around these kind of components and systems, together with dedicated space on the commonfare.net platform (perhaps in the form of a wiki or discussion forum) in which commoners can discuss such issues and reach consensus decisions.

The proposals sketched out above and laid out in more detail in the main body of this document are complex and ambitious. It is now up to the project consortium to decide which of them it wants to try out, and what to prioritize in terms of development time and resources.

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
AU	Abertay University
ANT	Actor-Network Theory
BIN-Italia	Basic Income Network Italia
CN/FBK	CREATE-NET/FBK
CPS	Centre for Peace Studies
MdC	Museu da Crise
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
Q&A	Question and Answer
WP	Work Package

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1. INTRODUCTION TO THIS REPORT

The goal of Work Package 3 (WP3) as laid out in the original PIE News project proposal has been ‘to specialize to PIE News [sic] of key research concepts supporting the social dynamics and long term sustainability of the project’ (PIE News, 2015, p52). Its work has centred on three key concepts/social dynamics relevant for the commonfare.net platform:

- ▶ Social capital and reputation;
- ▶ Digital currencies and value generation; and
- ▶ Social network dynamics.

The aim has been for WP3 to identify appropriate models for each of these concepts and offer solutions for the creation of online reputation systems, digital currencies and tools for network analysis and design of the project.

This deliverable builds on the work presented in our previous deliverable, D3.1 (Wilson et al, 2017), as well as empirical findings reported by the pilot partners in D2.1 (Fumagalli et al., 2017) and further co-design work carried out since the completion of both these documents.

As first suggested in D3.1, the empirical research conducted with pilot participants for both WP2 and WP3 has led us away from the form and function of conventional reputation systems in search of an approach that better reflects the experiences, desires and values of those who will constitute the commonfare.net community. In pursuit of this goal, we have ultimately combined our work on the first and third concepts, leading to an integrated presentation of a recognition and reward system based on network dynamics analysis. This new (and highly innovative) approach is born out of the overarching philosophy behind commonfare.net – that is, the cooperative, mutualistic approach to social welfare provision known as commonfare (Fumagalli and Lucarelli, 2015).

In order to properly contextualize both the empirical findings and proposals described in Chapters 3 and 4, Chapter 2 presents an overview of the commonfare concept, and the commonfare.net platform. It motivates the introduction of

the components/systems for the commonfare.net platform which are proposed in this document. Finally, it presents a novel conceptualization of interactions on a digital platform – a way of thinking that underpins the proposals integrating network dynamics analysis, trust, contribution and reward presented in Chapter 4. The various sections in this chapter are intended to explain the underlying thinking that, combined with the design input coming from the empirical research summarized in Chapter 3, led us to the proposals we present in Chapter 4. Chapter 2 includes both descriptive and conceptual elements in order to emphasise the symbiotic intellectual relationship between the core elements of a commonfare system and the conceptualization of commonfare.net as a fluid assemblage, constituted by relations between participants and digital objects, presented in Section 2.3.

Chapter 3 summarizes previous empirical work with potential commonfare.net participants at the pilot sites, and presents findings from additional work carried out since the production of D2.1 and D3.1. It emphasises the high importance placed on shared values, self-authorship, a sense of control and trust emerging from this research. In particular it reports on the strong desire of participants that commonfare.net should not replicate the more intrusive and manipulative or untrustworthy aspects of well-known platforms and technology companies such as Facebook and Google. It also highlights the openness of participants to experimenting with novel money systems, and some of the main features of a new money system that they would like (such as the absence of speculation, interest, and debt, and minimal forms of conditionality).

Chapter 4 draws on the ideas presented in Chapters 2 and 3 and puts forward proposals for various technical components/systems relating to digital currency or value token circulation, network analysis, trust, recognition and reward. It emphasises the connections between the different systems.

Proposals for implementing digital value tokens using two possible protocols (Faircoin2 and yetta) are presented.

The alternative approach to reputation first put forward in D3.1 (and the emphasis on recognizing contribution to interactions and cooperation rather than individualized success that that entailed) is further developed and elaborated. Practical ways in which these technical features might be implemented are presented, with particular emphasis on the use of network density metrics as opposed to reliance on inter-user ratings. Indeed, it proposes integrating network dynamics analysis algorithms with systems to recognize contributions that build the commonfare, facilitate trust and protect the community from platform misuse.

Work Package 3 draws to a close with this Deliverable. We would like to take the opportunity to thank the pilot teams (BIN-Italia, CPS and Museu da Crise) for their invaluable input. We would also like to thank Museu da Crise for their creative and productive help in the design of the most recent workshops and particularly the Commonpoly game (see Chapter 3 and internal workshop reports).

2. DESIGNING A COLLECTIVE AWARENESS PLATFORM FOR THE COMMONFARE: CURRENCY, CONTRIBUTION AND TRUST

This chapter provides an overview of the philosophical and conceptual background to the PIE News project and the development of the commonfare.net platform (Botto and Teli, 2017; PIE News, 2015), and the implications this background has for aspects of the platform's implementation of complementary currency or digital value tokens and social dynamics affordances and features. It is essential that this conceptual background is reflected in proposals for the design of components/systems that allow the circulation of one or more currencies, and that are intended to facilitate constructive, cooperative interactions that will contribute to building the commonfare.

We first present (in section 2.1) an introduction to the commonfare concept.

Next, Section 2.2 describes the overall structure and intentions of the commonfare.net platform, with an emphasis on how it may support practical development of the commonfare among users at an abstract or general level (the characteristics and requirements of the pilot contexts are discussed in Chapters 3 and 4). Section 2.2.1 describes the broad structure of the platform as initially planned in the project proposal, and how that has developed within the project to date. Following this, in section 2.2.2, we describe the role of a complementary, digital currency within the digital commonfare approach. The introduction of a digital currency or exchange token that may be used for online transactions between users increases the need for mechanisms to help users establish trust with both the platform and each other. This need is increased still further by the goal of the project to have practical impact on people's lives, and so to encourage online interactions to develop into face-to-face or community associations that act in the hybrid of virtual and physical spaces. Section 2.2.3 describes the need to help users to develop and/or sustain trust. Section 2.2 concludes with section 2.2.4, which deals

with the need to detect and act on platform/currency misuse.

Section 2.3 presents a conceptualization of commonfare.net and how activities on the platform can be conceived of as building and expanding the commonfare. Its starting point is a particular conceptualization of commonfare.net as a network or assemblage, drawing on ideas first developed in the field of Science and Technology Studies, particularly Actor-Network Theory (Callon, 1984; Latour, 1987, 2005; Law, 2009) and Assemblage Theory (DeLanda, 2016). We suggest that adopting this perspective means it is more likely that the values of cooperation and autonomy inherent in commonfare are diffused throughout the design of the components/systems within the remit of WP3.

2.1 WHAT IS COMMONFARE?

This section provides a brief introduction to the key features of a commonfare approach to social welfare, so that the reader can understand what the proposals laid out in this document are intended to facilitate.

The PIE News project is dedicated to the development of a mobile-first, web-based platform through which to improve the lives of people experiencing precarious income and employment conditions through the promotion and facilitation of commonfare, an alternative approach to social welfare (Fumagalli and Lucarelli, 2015). A commonfare approach is grounded in the recognition that the social and economic are not separate spheres, but instead are inextricably and intricately connected. Commonfare is:

- ▶ bottom-up
- ▶ socially equitable
- ▶ cooperative

As illustrated in Figure 1, key features of a commonfare approach include proper management of the common (both physical commons such as water, land and so on and immaterial commons such as knowledge and affect); an unconditional, basic income for all; and the development of complementary financial circuits.

Figure 1: The three pillars of a Commonfare approach to social welfare

It should be stressed that commonfare is not intended to replace social welfare provision from State actors, but rather to supplement it and return some control of welfare to the people.

Any digital platform that attempts to encourage a commonfare approach must therefore have design processes and features that are consistent with its core principles of bottom-up, socially equitable and cooperative action.

2.2 THE COMMONFARE.NET CONCEPT

Commonfare.net is intended to be a collective awareness platform that facilitates the development of commonfare approaches to social welfare among its users. Commonfare.net will offer a complementary channel for the provision of social welfare, allowing users to take better advantage of State offerings as well as to create their own alternative support and empowerment mechanisms. (For a deeper understanding of the aims of the project, see Botto and Teli (2017).)

This section provides a brief overview of commonfare.net, in order to furnish the reader with the context for the platform components/systems that are the design responsibility of WP3. These fall into three broad categories: digital currency systems, systems to encourage constructive, cooperative interactions and systems to discourage and/or correct platform misuse. These are briefly introduced, with indications of how they will contribute to building a platform that facilitates a commonfare approach.

2.2.1 Commonfare.net structure

Commonfare.net will be a platform with three core features:

- ▶ information provision,
- ▶ story-telling, and
- ▶ active support.

These can be thought of as interacting with each other as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The broad structure of the commonfare.net platform

Drilling down deeper, the intentions are that the three strands of the platform will include the following:

- ▶ Informing:
 - state provisions
 - informal initiatives
 - educational opportunities
- ▶ Inspiring/motivating:
 - sharing “good practices”
 - story-telling
- ▶ Supporting action:
 - transactions, sharing economy
 - group creation / cooperation
 - forums for supportive Q&A

For more detail, see Botto and Teli (2017).

The first platform release, early in 2017, began to implement the “informing” function through the initial provision of information about policies relating to work, social services, housing, mobility, education and training, and cultural events specific to the pilot sites. The second release, scheduled for autumn 2017, will start to make the platform more interactive by implementing registration, profile creation and story-telling facilities. Subsequent releases will allow more types of interaction.

By allowing a range of different types of connection and interaction – some lasting, some more fleeting – commonfare.net will create a networked assemblage of users and digital resources. The density and level of activity within this network will then be an indication of the strength or value of the commonfare. In order to create a strong and sustainable network, we need to develop, trial and implement components/systems that encourage participation and exchange, facilitate trust and recognize positive contributions to the commonfare. Three of these are the responsibility of WP3, and are the subjects of this deliverable. These are introduced in the next three sections, and their potential contribution to building a sustainable commonfare community are outlined.

2.2.2 The circulation of a complementary digital currency as part of the commonfare

The first system intended to help build the commonfare that we present is a cryptographically-secured digital exchange token.

As indicated in Section 2.1, the creation and use of complementary currency systems for the social good is an integral part of a commonfare approach (Fumagalli and Lucarelli, 2015), and so the implementation of one or more digital currency solutions has been a key intention since the beginning of the PIE News project (PIE News, 2015).

The introduction of tailor-made digital currency or exchange token systems may bring several benefits to the commonfare.net platform and its users.

For example, a digital currency may be used for the exchange of goods, services and skills made available through the commonfare.net platform via the use of digital exchange tokens. Complementary digital currencies may offer ways to stimulate interactions and so break down boundaries between communities that might otherwise find it difficult to share skills, resources, and ideas. Indeed, the possibility of breaking down barriers between geographically separated or previously unconnected, but ideologically or philosophically similar groups is clearly something that will be an important way of building and strengthening the common wealth on which commonfare.net will depend.

As described in Section 2.1, one of the pillars of a commonfare approach is the provision of an unconditional, universal basic income. Basic income may be provisioned within the commonfare.net platform using the digital coin that the consortium ultimately selects. However, as will be shown in Chapter 3, the question remains as to whether members of the pilot communities want an unconditional and universal basic income.

In designing digital exchange tokens for commonfare.net, we first need to look at the experiences, desires and values of the participants being engaged in the pilots by project partners BIN-Italia, CPS and Museu da Crise. These participants include precarious workers of all ages (including those working in freelance capacity), young unemployed people, benefit recipients and non-Western migrants. One can easily imagine that different digital currency/exchange token features will be needed to accommodate the different situations and financial patterns of these groups. For

example, as described in D3.1, in the Italian pilot, a pre-existing collectivist group of freelance/precarious workers in Milan has already been experimenting with a digital currency as a means to distribute money (ultimately in euros) amongst those members that contribute substantially to the functioning of the collective. While this has proved to be a successful implementation of a complementary money system intended to facilitate a bottom-up approach to basic income, the project team has to consider how this can be transferred to less well-defined, pre-existing groups. For example, if commonfare.net is to provide a cryptographically-secured digital exchange token through which a (universal, unconditional) basic income can be implemented across the pilots, it needs to be able to do so for individuals who are not members of collectives, as well as collectives that do not generate income from external sources.

Equally importantly, if a digital coin is introduced in order to function as an exchange token that is internal to commonfare.net and so facilitates mutual skills, knowledge and resource exchange, it needs to be designed so as to conform to the principles of a commonfare approach – including collective ownership of the money system as a common good.

In addition, it is vitally important for the sustainability and growth of the platform that we consider the possibility to scale up to address societal challenges common to people living in precarious financial and employment conditions beyond the immediate scope of the pilots.

These, then, are some of the design issues the WP3 currency design team faced as they developed proposals for the circulation of digital currencies or cryptographically-secured exchange tokens on commonfare.net.

2.2.3 The need for systems that facilitate trust, and encourage and recognize positive contributions to the commonfare

The second set of components/systems that WP3 is responsible for is those that will help stabilize and grow the platform by facilitating trust and encouraging constructive, cooperative contributions to the commonfare. Such systems require monitoring of platform use and platform-based interactions, and so as will be described in Chapter 4 may best be achieved using the tools of dynamic network analysis.

As described above, the philosophy behind commonfare.net is one that values the provision of mutual support and activities that lead to communal benefit. This means that cooperation and collaborative action will be essential to the development of a strong and valuable commonfare. To achieve this, the platform will offer various ways for people to interact; and as in the physical world, trust will be important in facilitating and encouraging interactions.

Trust is a fundamental component of social relations. It helps actors make decisions in situations where direct knowledge that can guide action is not always immediately available, and when action entails some risk. In other words, trust helps reduce complexity in social interactions, allowing actors to enabling decisions that might otherwise

be difficult (Luhman, 1979). While trust is often seen as a relation between one individual (trustor) and another one (trustee) in relation to an object or outcome, it can also take a collective form in what is known as reputation, or how a community or group of people view the trustworthiness of another person or another entity.

When people interact in the physical world, they base decisions on whom to interact with on information about a person's past behaviour, and a sense of shared values (Jones and George, 1998). Depending on the nature of the interaction, different levels of trust may be required and so different standards of evidence relied on. For example, if a person wants to buy something – a second-hand clarinet, say – offered for sale in a private transaction by another person, her decision of whether to buy or not is more likely to be influenced by the perceived quality of the clarinet, and the level of value-for-money, than by issues of trust. However, if the same person (trustor) needs someone to look after her children (object of trust) for a couple of hours in the evening while she goes for a clarinet lesson, she will be far more interested in the past behaviour of prospective child-minders (trustees), and their reputation for trustworthiness. If she is not familiar with the person herself, she may seek the opinions of others in the form of reputation.

The same person will also make decision about actions based on trust in larger entities. For example, if she wants to buy a new washing machine, her decision on which shop to go to will be influenced by a variety of factors including advertising, reputation of both the manufacturer and the shop, past experiences and, again, perceived value-for-money.

However, when an interaction is for the purposes of sharing personal – possibly intimate – information, or for participation in a group endeavour such as a campaign, then the person's perception of shared values will be far more important. This, again, can be on an individual level (“*Is this person like me?*”) or at the level of a larger organization (“*This campaign is supported by this charity, which I trust and have respect for. This suggests the organizers of the campaign share some of my values.*”).

Interacting in a digital environment requires similar judgments (Hsu et al., 2007; Usoro et al., 2007). Indeed research from the pilot partners showed both that trust in formal institutions was decreasing amongst study participants, and that this mistrust was also mirrored in the digital world, increasing the value and need for trust between individuals. It is thus important that commonfare.net has built into it systems that facilitate judgments of trustworthiness. Deliverable D3.1 included a survey and analysis of the kind of systems that are commonly used to establish trust/reputation in online environments. It concluded that a different approach needs to be developed for commonfare.net, largely because existing systems based on ratings and accumulation of reputation in the forms of, e.g., points or stars do not seem to be properly aligned with the core idea of commonfare; also, in interviews and focus groups, they were rejected as a way to build trust by many pilot participants (see D3.1 and section 3.2 of this deliverable).

As well as systems to help facilitate judgments about interactions, we also want to recognize that those interactions are essential to build the commonfare that commonfare.net will support. In the initial proposal for this project, it was suggested to link a reputation system to rewards in the form of the digital currency. As will be discussed in Chapter 3, this link may not be strongly welcomed by some potential participants; however, a system that recognizes participants' actions that strengthen the commonfare seems to be felt to be desirable. Such a system may encourage participation and thus help make the platform more sustainable.

As well as providing individuals with recognition of their contributions to commonfare.net, a system that monitors and identifies actions that strengthen the platform will be useful to the platform itself. If some participants are more effective than others at spreading information about good practices and/or initiatives, then the platform may target them with particular updates about ideas that need to be spread widely and/or quickly.

2.2.4 The need for systems to identify misuse

The final set of components/systems that WP3 proposes to help build the commonfare are those that help identify platform misuse. As with facilitation of trust and encouragement of positive contributions, this will require monitoring and analysis of the platform's network dynamics.

In the pilot phase, most of those who participate on commonfare.net are likely to be well-motivated, as they have been brought into the project through their contact with the pilot partners, BIN-Italia, CPS and Museu da Crise. During this contact, they are likely to have been at least partially convinced of the value of participating. However, in any digital system involving a digital currency, or rewards that potentially give privileges, there is a risk that some will seek to exploit it for personal gain. Looking to the longer term for commonfare.net, we therefore need to build into the platform systems that examine activity within the network (the way the currency or exchange tokens circulate, patterns of interactions between participants) and look for evidence of behaviours that detract from the commonfare.

For example, if participants are rewarded for contributions that appear to be valued by others, they may seek to increase their rewards by colluding with others who falsely indicate appreciation or approval of their contributions. Alternatively, they may hoard quantities of the digital currency, thus taking it out of circulation and effectively reducing its value to the commonfare. Or in extreme cases, they may even seek to engage in financial practices that, while not uncommon in the conventional economic system, are counter to the building of the commonfare, such as lending at interest or even fraudulent or extortionate behaviour. It is therefore important that the platform design include features that make such behaviours difficult, if not impossible. We therefore propose possible monitoring mechanisms that may help to identify when such behaviours are in play.

This section (Section 2.2) has outlined the basic features of commonfare.net and explained the need for systems that

both allow a digital currency to circulate and that monitor that circulation and activities more broadly across the platform. The following section describes how a particular conceptualization of commonfare.net (and the commonfare it supports) leads naturally to particular ways to implement such systems.

2.3 CONCEPTUALIZING COMMONFARE.NET AS AN ASSEMBLAGE OF USERS AND DIGITAL OBJECTS

In this section, we present a way of conceptualizing commonfare.net and the way in which activities on the platform add value to the commonfare. We propose to consider commonfare.net as an assemblage of users (henceforth referred to as commoners) and digital objects (such as stories, profiles, images, videos, web pages and hyperlinks). This assemblage allows for flows of information, knowledge, practical support and affect (including trust). The digital currency or exchange tokens can also be thought of as circulating within and across its boundaries.

2.3.1 The commonfare.net assemblage

Commonfare.net is, at its heart, a project that relies on the participation and actions of those that engage with it. It will take the form of a networked community of users, henceforth referred to as commoners. The WP3 team conceive of commonfare.net as an assemblage of commoners and digital resources. Within this assemblage, information, knowledge, good practice and affect will circulate.

Our conceptualization draws on ideas first developed in the field of Science and Technology Studies, especially Actor-Network Theory or ANT (Callon, 1984; Latour, 1987, 2005; Law, 2009) and Assemblage Theory (Delanda, 2016). Within these approaches, the notion of an assemblage extends that of a network by:

- ▶ acknowledging that it is not a static network, but is one that is continuously produced and re-produced;
- ▶ envisaging each element of the network as also itself continuously produced and re-produced as a nexus of time-varying relations;
- ▶ emphasising the possibility of emergent behaviours and possibilities for collective action;
- ▶ recognizing that agency is distributed within the assemblage rather than inherent in (and the sole responsibility of) individuals;
- ▶ concomitantly recognizing that the assemblage as a whole needs to act in ways that help it survive and grow.

That is, the idea of an assemblage recognizes that the whole network, has properties and behaviours that develop as it seeks to sustain itself and expand through the recruitment of new participants. As described by Fenwick and Edwards,

Actor-network theory examines the associations of human and non-human entities in the performance of the social, the economic, the natural, the educational, etc. The objective is to understand precisely how these things

come together – and manage to hold together, however temporarily – to form associations that produce agency and other effects: for example ideas, identities, rules, routines, policies, instruments, and reforms.

(2010, p3, emphasis in original)

In Actor-Network Theory (ANT), the assemblage is composed of actants (the nodes in the network) and the relations between them – the term actants is used instead of actors because the latter is usually reserved for humans rather than non-human, material or digital objects. In addition, actant is used to signal the fact that these assemblage components simultaneously act and are acted upon. That is, from an ANT perspective, both human and non-human are considered equally important in the emergence of agency, knowledge, trust and so on as effects of the network, and actants themselves are understood as products of the relationships between them (Latour, 1987; 2005).

This conception of both the commonfare (as being created through the activities in the assemblage) and commonfare.net (as an assemblage or actor-network) provides a perspective from which to consider several important aspects of online social dynamics.

For example, an ANT perspective reminds us to pay attention to the relations between humans and non-humans (in the commonfare.net case, digital resources). It also suggests that, because actants are the products of the relationships that connect them in the assemblage, anyone seeking to understand an assemblage might do well to start from the interactions and connections rather than from individual nodes.

ANT also offers a way to think about those components of an assemblage that are particularly effective at enrolling other actants. Latour (1987, 2005) and Law and Singleton (2005; Law, 2009) put forward the idea of (im)mutable mobiles:

An immutable mobile ... [is an actant] that moves around but also holds its shape ... in some relational and possibly functional manner where it may, to say it quickly, be imagined as a more or less stable network of associations.

(Law and Singleton, 2005, p335)

Law and Singleton (2005) describe how (im)mutable mobiles contribute to long-distance control and the circulation of facts through an assemblage:

Empires ... hold themselves together because immutable mobiles circulate in and through narrow net-works that allow them to retain their shape. Codes, information, people such as technicians, soldiers or bankers, technological bits and pieces such as ships or scientific instruments, texts such as orders, newspapers or money orders—if objects such as these are able to hold their relational shape as they circulate around the globe, then long-distance control is a possibility. ... [Such control] depends upon a process in which networks of relations are built up to secure immutability on the one hand, and mobility on the other ... On the one hand, [objects] probably have a more or less stable shape in physical space—though the definition of that stable physical shape is likely to depend on relational and interactive work of one kind or another ... On the other hand, they

certainly have, display or are constituted by a more or less stable structure in a network of relations. Stability ... is sustained in two separate and partially related ways ... The added ANT argument is that it takes **effort** to sustain stable networks of relations.

(Law and Singleton, 2005, pp335-337, emphasis in original)

While in commonfare.net we are not dealing with issues of control per se. the same concept of more or less immutable objects as being important for the stability and sustainability of the network as a whole may be helpful in thinking about the role of particular digital objects such as stories, or abstract objects such as good practices. Critically, we have to recognize that it takes effort to sustain the stability of the networks of relations that constitute such digital and abstract objects. That is, the platform needs systems that help maintain this stability.

Callon (1984) describes four key phases in the creation and expansion of a successful (i.e. sustainable) actor-network or assemblage (what he calls "moments of translation"):

► **Problematization** - the initial creation of an actor-network assemblage through the interdefinition of interested actors together with the problem to be addressed or action programme to be initiated. For comonfare.net, this moment or phase corresponds to the interactions between the pilot partners and members of the target communities, with the intention of engaging these actors in the definition and creation of the commonfare.net platform itself. There is also a programme of action in the form of the promotion of the notion and practice of commonfare.

► **Interessement** - the second phase where the primary actors who begin to interact during problematization attract other actors into the network. For commonfare.net, this would correspond to the bootstrapping phase, during which members of the pilot communities begin to register on the platform and upload initial stories, and early interactions and online connections begin to form.

► **Enrolment** - the moment or phase when actors are enrolled as actants in the emerging actor-network, so that their actions become both shaped by and essential to the sustainability and growth of the actor-network. In the commonfare.net context, this phase would correspond to the establishment of a group of committed commoners and the aggregation of digital objects such as stories and representations of good practice that serve to create and strengthen the commonfare.net assemblage.

► **Mobilization** - during this phase, some actants emerge as spokesmen who both represent other, more passive network actors (agents) and seek to mobilize them (enrol them as actants), thus creating a stronger and more stable actor-network.

All four phases of translation involve negotiations among human and non-human actants, in which common sets of definitions and meanings for understanding the phenomena with which the network is concerned are arrived at, and common values are established. The outcome of successful negotiations is an actor-network characterized by aligned interests. As will be shown in Chapter 3, this notion of

Figure 3: Representing a networked community graphically

negotiation and the importance of shared meanings and values was an extremely important theme emerging from interviews, focus groups and workshops with potential commoners from the pilot communities, further supporting the usefulness of an ANT perspective.

Indeed, there may be commoners who are particularly effective at connecting others or spreading information, or who start initiatives that attract others. Or there may be stories that gain a lot of attention, or initiatives/campaigns that get a lot of support. These can be understood as actants in the commonfare.net assemblage that are involved in the intersement and enrolment of others.

The notions of problematization and intersement, and the associated idea of 'obligatory passage points' (Callon, 1984), may help us to think about what causes a casual visitor to commit and become an enrolled commoner. We shall not know until the commonfare.net assemblage starts to develop, but perhaps there will be obligatory passage points, for example experiences of support, value or congruence, that are necessary before new actants are enrolled.

Figures 3 to 5 illustrate how these ideas may be visualized. As no interaction data is available as yet for commonfare.net, these graphs draw on other data sources.

Figure 3 is a representation of a social network, similar to the community of commoners that commonfare.net hopes to create. It is based on the data for the Financial Problems and Unemployment Support Group discussion forums

described in Deliverable 3.1. The nodes in this network graph represent members of the community and the lines between them represent interactions between members in the form of posts and replies on the discussion forums.

The graph in Figure 3 is one possible visualization of the assemblage of participants in which information, advice and emotional support can circulate. The more paths there are connecting participants, the more channels there are along which such attributes can flow. The strength of the community lies in these flows, which can potentially alter the lives and experiences of those who are part of it.

In this representation, the size of a node corresponds to the number of connections it has to other nodes. A strong network is then one that has a high density and many large nodes, indicating that many participants in the community are connected with each other. This kind of visualization also helps to identify participants who are more or less important in binding the network together. For example, some participants are at the centre of complex networks of relations, and contribute a sizeable amount to the density of the graph. Others, such as those in the bottom right corner who are not connected to any others, appear to be only peripheral actors in the discussion forum assemblage. Part of the work of the WP3 team is to consider the social dynamics that lead to these differences, and ways of modelling and responding to them that might more successfully integrate those who are currently more isolated.

Figure 4: Alternative representation of the same networked community

As stated above, Figure 3 is just one possible representation of the discussion forum assemblage. Figure 4 presents the same community and interactions but with a different property determining the size of the nodes.

In this graph, the size of the nodes indicates the number of points the user has acquired in the discussion forum's reputation system (see D3.1).

One can see that the relative size of some of the more hub-like nodes changes between Figures 3 and 4, but the

sizes of the least connected nodes (those with less than five connections) is unchanged, suggesting that the two measures are reasonably consistent in identifying those who are not heavily involved.

In the commonfare.net context, such graphs might include a range of different interaction types, such as following, friending, being a member of the same group, or engaging in an exchange of services, skills or goods. This will result in a range of possible network representations, which might be examined separately or in aggregate.

Podgornykh et al. 2014

Figure 5: A graphical representation of an assemblage of participants and digital resources

The expanded idea of a networked assemblage of commoners and digital resources is illustrated by the graph in Figure 5. In this figure, participants in the community are represented by coloured circles and the digital resources they connect to are represented by black squares.

This image has been constructed from data concerning interactions between participants in a Twitter chat held among practicing school teachers (Wilson, 2016). The types of interaction included in the graph are retweets, likes and replies. The coloured circles represent Twitter users and the black squares are the tweets they interact with. Again, the size of the nodes corresponds to the number of interactions they are associated with. As in the previous graphs, a strong network is one with many connections, and in which there are many large nodes, whether they are participants or digital objects. In the commonfare.net context, similar graphs could be constructed for interactions between commoners and digital objects such as information resources, stories, and/or web pages presenting groups or

initiatives.

This view of activity on commonfare.net also suggests that graph theoretical techniques can be applied to identify (im)mutable mobiles, obligatory passage points, and so on. Mathematical (social) network measures such as closeness and betweenness centrality, PageRank, k-core-ness etc. can be used to identify these actants and recognize (and potentially reward) their contribution, or identify them as stories or initiatives to highlight to site visitors in the hope of developing interest and ultimately to their enrolment.

The suggestions made in Chapter 4 of this report are underpinned by this conceptualization of commonfare.net and the strength and value of the commonfare it helps to create. However, they are also influenced by empirical data from the co-design process undertaken as part of WP2 and WP3. The next chapter, Chapter 3, describes these data.

2.4 SUMMARY

This chapter has provided a description of the conceptual context for WP3's work, including:

- ▶ The concept of commonfare;
- ▶ The concept of a digital platform for commonfare, and the introduction of platform elements intended to imbue it with commonfare characteristics, i.e.
 - Complementary money systems;
 - Systems to encourage cooperative, mutualistic behaviour (trust and recognition/reward);
 - Systems to discourage behaviour that might diminish the common wealth; and
- ▶ The conceptualization of such a platform as an actor-network or networked assemblage.

Before going on to describe proposals for the necessary components/systems, we need to provide in addition details of the empirical context. This is what Chapter 3 sets out to do.

3. COMMONFARE.NET: EMPIRICAL CONTEXT

As a participatory co-design project, commonfare.net is being developed for, with and by potential commoners. This chapter presents relevant findings from empirical work conducted through WP2 and WP3 to date.

3.1 EARLY WORK OF THE PILOT PARTNERS: D2.1

Deliverable D2.1 (Fumagalli et al., 2017) was produced by WP2, through the parallel and cooperative research of the pilot partners BIN-Italia in Italy, CPS in Croatia and Museu da Crise in the Netherlands.

This deliverable included a survey of the types of bottom-up welfare that are already spontaneously developing in each of the three pilot countries. It showed how social cooperation is already able to provide some answers to the difficulties faced by those experiencing financial and employment precarity. Commonfare.net aims to highlight such “good practices” and emphasise their emergence from the people rather than provision or imposition from authorities, thus hopefully making them appear more feasible to others. In addition, sharing and spreading stories of effective steps taken to improve the lives of people in the pilot communities is intended to facilitate a community-building process. Thus it is important for WP3, which includes network dynamic analysis and the development of mechanisms to facilitate the likelihood of interactions (particularly trusting interactions), to consider what mechanisms can be put in place to ensure the most effective diffusion through the commonfare.net assemblage of such stories.

In D2.1, WP2 stressed several points that were felt to be particularly important for the development of the commonfare.net platform.

One point (strongly echoed in the findings reported in D3.1) was the need to feel agency over one's life. This might be in the form of being free from conditionalities placed on one by the State; being able to decide to start a family; being able to run one's own business; being able to choose what to work on, and how much of one's time to devote to work activities; to travel; to choose what, when and how to learn;

and, for the young Croatians, to be in a position to move out of the family home.

Another finding, most pressing in the Netherlands but also an issue in Italy and to some extent Croatia, was hidden poverty in the form of debt – that is, the fact that people who appear on the surface to have adequate incomes may actually be experiencing severe precarity due to personal debt. This finding was reinforced in the interviews conducted in parallel in WP3 and reported on in D3.1, as it was found that some respondents who had their own homes and therefore did not appear to be at risk of housing precarity were having to take on multiple jobs in order to maintain mortgage payments, and so on. While the research reported in D2.1 was unable to delineate the social make-up of the fraction of the populations experiencing indebtedness, the authors of the report speculated that freelancers and welfare recipients might feature particularly strongly. This finding has substantial implications for the design of any digital currency system for commonfare.net, indicating for example that indebtedness should not be possible within it.

The final point emphasised in D2.1 that is relevant to the proposals made in the current deliverable relates to new forms of solidarity and fragmentation. D2.1 reported that while social divisions are deepening and negatively impacting solidarity on a national level in each pilot country, new forms of solidarity are emerging, and there appears to be a common desire for people to feel themselves part of a community. The authors suggested that self-organized forms of solidarity emerging in distributed networks, associations and (citizen) collectives may indicate a reversal of individualization, but also represents an exclusive form of solidarity that extends mainly to people with similar interests and a common background. From the WP3 point of view, this is important in relation to the circulation of knowledge, practice and affect (including trust, in particular) within the commonfare.net assemblage. It may be important to use network dynamics analysis to identify when barriers between subgroups form or act to obstruct what could be cooperative interactions that are both mutually beneficial and that contribute to the strength of the assemblage as a whole.

3.2 EARLY EMPIRICAL WORK WITHIN WP3: D3.1

The main findings from the work leading to D3.1 (Wilson et al., 2017) that inform the proposals in the next chapter of this document can be summarized as follows:

- ▶ Reputation systems are common features of transactional/trading sites and expert Q&A sites, but less frequently feature on community support sites.
- ▶ Conventional reputation systems are almost always based on a highly individualistic, acquisitive model which effectively commoditizes “reputation” and risks hollowing out cooperation and trust at the human level. Such systems seem to be philosophically at odds with the principles of cooperation and contribution to the common good inherent to a commonfare approach.
- ▶ Those experiencing financial precarity in the target groups at the pilot sites have varied experiences and aspirations, but there are some commonalities in terms of values and relationships. In particular, relationships with the State, bureaucracy and the corporate world seemed to be widely perceived as negative or, at best, neutral through irrelevance; and qualities such as independence and dignity are highly valued.
- ▶ Social capital in the form of family and friendship ties is critical to many people’s management of precarity, as is a sense of social contribution or vocation. Users of commonfare.net are as likely to be seeking affective support and a sense of community as practical help.
- ▶ In general, precarious financial and employment conditions are likely to be associated with stress, anxiety and depression. We therefore need to avoid creating yet another sphere (for example, that of online reputation or wealth in digital currency) in which people can experience poverty, precarity or social exclusion.
- ▶ The co-design and trial of a digital currency system in a community at the Milan site showed how effective this process can be in meeting a group of users’ needs; however it also raised questions about how to transfer and grow this tailor-made system to less well-defined groups with less well-defined tasks to complete and be rewarded for.

All these factors seemed to suggest that we should move away from conventional notions of individual and accumulating reputation, towards a system where reward is for interactions that contribute to the building of the commonfare.

3.3 ONGOING CO-DESIGN WORK

Since the production of D3.1, further empirical research has been conducted with the specific aim of feeding into

the design of the digital currency, contribution-recognition and possible reward systems. This research includes two workshops and two sessions of the game Commonpoly (designed by Museu da Crise) with freelancers in Amsterdam.

3.3.1 Preliminary workshop on trust and currency, June 2017

The initial workshop on trust and currency was held as part of the Design Workshop 3 activities undertaken in Amsterdam in June 2017. There were ten participants, all of whom were freelancers experiencing precarious financial and/or employment conditions.

In the first part of the workshop, participants were asked to identify issues that were currently important to them. Consistent with the findings reported in D2.1 and D3.1, issues raised included:

- ▶ being fed-up with the uncertainty of freelance conditions;
- ▶ being “between many jobs”;
- ▶ expressing concern that freelance status was no longer real, in constrained working conditions such as for example working full-time for a single employer but without contract or concomitant benefits, certainty and stability;
- ▶ evident pride in current work/projects; and
- ▶ comment on the mercenary origin of the word freelancer.

This last point is an interesting observation that suggests a certain ambivalence towards freelance status, similar to the question of whether it is a reality or something of an illusion. It also highlights the importance of words and language, an issue that has arisen several times in the project. It also connects with comments made in the follow-up workshop held in August in relation to visual language (see below) and the military connotations of a stars-based rating system.

What should the site be like?

Presaging more lengthy discussions in the August workshop, participants made it clear that they did not want ‘another Facebook.’ For one person, this was simply because Facebook was already doing much of what the freelancers themselves described as what they wished to find on commonfare.net:

What I read in [the post-it notes] – exchange of goods, community, fellowship – that’s already in Face-book and other social networks, where people are familiar and they already connect. So I think that’s not a strength, if you propose the same thing. Exchange of goods. People are doing this bottom-up via groups.

However, this led to a strong response from other participants, who expressed serious mistrust of Facebook:

It’s an extremely perverted way ... Big Brother ... it’s an incredible track and trace way.

This led to a discussion about how people use Facebook (which reflected findings already reported in D3.1 and used to build the user scenarios presented in that document). It also prefigured the extended discussion of the importance of commonfare.net having clear values if it is to be trusted (see below).

Contribution/trust mechanism

We picked up on this discussion (of the difference between trading and mutual aid/exchange, and distrust of Facebook etc.) to introduce the idea of a contribution-recognition system and its potential link to the digital currency via a reward system.

The initial response to this from one participant was a very strong,

No ... it introduces competition, and that's the kind of thing I would like to avoid.

Another participant asked whether commonfare.net could emulate time banks and reward people in time, rather than currency.

On the question of whether there should be a system for contribution-recognition with publicly visible contribution metrics, divorced from reward in digital currency or value tokens, the discussion was quite different. The same participant who had responded with the strong “No” initially now said she would definitely like it, and brought up the issue of establishing trust. Another participant noted how difficult it is to establish trust and agree value online (again similar to some of the findings reported in D3.1).

In relation to trust and reputation, one participant mentioned StackOverflow as something that we could model our system on, but then modified his comment with the statement,

Developers are one thing, and these topics are quite different.

When asked whether they would be comfortable having a rating system associated with the kinds of things that will be talked about/done on commonfare.net, the answer was a fairly clear “No”. Issues raised were that StackOverflow, Wikipedia etc. are fine for rating because the topics are factual/technical, but that anything where it is about real/personal life should not have ratings associated with it. Again, these comments support suggestions made in D3.1.

Characteristics of the site that would encourage/deter participation

The participants in this workshop gave a range of features that would be important to their decision to participate in and contribute to the site. These can be divided into issues relating to the site’s apparent values, ethos and purpose, and (associated) practical issues.

Characteristics that were described as important for encouraging participation are listed below. Most important

seemed to be a sense of shared values. Comments relating to the site’s values and ethos included:

- ▶ common ground,
- ▶ feeling that one can contribute as well as get help (and, perhaps because of this, that getting help would be a guilt-free experience),
- ▶ feeling that it is a cooperative space,
- ▶ feeling that participation in the commonfare is rewarding,
- ▶ not feeling obliged to contribute,
- ▶ a sense that the platform operates in a transparent way,
- ▶ a sense of safety and trust,
- ▶ equality,
- ▶ fairness,
- ▶ awareness, and
- ▶ quality.

As one participant put it, what was important to them was:

... feeling that by participating, you are a part of something beautiful!

There were also related practical issues, including:

- ▶ a safe review/rating system (if such a system was implemented at all),
- ▶ an easy and clear way to connect with others; low barriers and easy “user flows”; avoid complexity,
- ▶ the establishment of mini-communities,
- ▶ feeling that the system works and is helpful or useful,
- ▶ getting the services I need, and
- ▶ well-organized offerings of skills/goods.

The primary reasons for being deterred from engaging with commonfare.net related to the ethos of the platform, especially in relation to cooperation, trust and privacy:

- ▶ people advertising their business; commercial activities; selling,
- ▶ ratings systems,
- ▶ competition/competitiveness instead of cooperation,
- ▶ exclusion,
- ▶ aggressive language,
- ▶ users not being valued,
- ▶ lack of trust; The realization that others are misusing the platform,
- ▶ complex or limited privacy settings,
- ▶ being tracked/monitored (“They know who I am”)

- ▶ any connection with (e.g. log-in through) Facebook or similar, and
- ▶ just another social network.

People also cited practical issues that would put them off the site and make it less likely for them to participate:

- ▶ engagement being time-consuming; spending too much time, and
- ▶ too complex.

One response summed up participants' feelings with the comment that they would be put off from using the system if they 'realis[ed] the platform doesn't achieve what is intended.' Others raised related questions:

How can we make communities SUSTAINABLE? What keeps them from falling apart?

Digital platforms are often ruled by the strong/tough – how can commonfare.net support “the weak”?

- ▶ interactions with the platform; and
- ▶ what to reveal to others about one's activities on the platform.

One of the most important factors determining whether participants felt a website or platform was trustworthy was evidence about how it approached privacy and data ownership:

... if it was sharing information with other things, that might make me suspicious about what it was... In the same ways that we get – that Google does, that you know when you're surfing for different things, and then you see like banners and ads that are about the things you were looking for. ... when I can see that my information is being used to target me, for money, then that would make me go ok what's going on here.

3.3.2 Main workshop on trust, contribution and reward

A second workshop was held in Amsterdam in 2017, again involving freelancers experiencing precarious conditions. The focus-group nature of the discussions in this workshop mean that, although the views expressed below are those of individuals, there were opportunities for other participants to disagree or present alternative arguments. Because of the way that Museu da Crise works with participants in their pilot, those at the workshop were keenly aware that their comments would influence the design of the commonfare.net in real and practical ways, and so not only did they take the discussions seriously, they were also likely to explicitly reject ideas that they felt were bad.

This workshop was attended by five participants sampling a range of nationalities (both Southern and Northern European states) and spheres of expertise/current income-generation situations. Workshop activities addressed five broad areas:

- ▶ Establishing trust in the platform itself.
- ▶ Deciding whether to interact with others.
- ▶ Recognition of contributions to the commonfare.
- ▶ Representations of contributions.
- ▶ Reward for contributions.

Establishing trust in the platform itself

Following up on the discussions in the preliminary workshop reported in section 3.3.1 above, participants were first asked what features would make them immediately distrustful of a site (commonfare.net in particular), and so likely to leave without participating.

A sense of having control, in a variety of forms, was a critical factor for developing trust. Particularly important seemed to be having a sense that one controlled

- ▶ one's own data;

Participants wanted to be sure that only the platform they had chosen to access or the service they had chosen to use had access to data about their usage, and that these data were not going to be passed on to third parties.

Related to this was a dislike of sites that made participants feel they did not have control over their interactions. Sites that tricked them into signing up to unwanted newsletters through the extensive use of pre-ticked boxes in registration processes were singled out as ones they disliked, as were any sites that they felt were trying to manipulate them in some way:

If er an organization or a web service is trying to be clever, I really distrust it ... I like it if what you see is what you get, you know? Just be honest what it is, and if you're trying to be clever and you're trying to fool me, then you have to be really smart, because if I feel like you're fooling me then I get annoyed. And then I'm off.

The other critical factor was being able to see and understand a sites purpose. This was described in terms of the site having clarity about its purpose:

... before I even enter the platform. Why I have been targeted to come here ... so transparency about what it is about ... Because I think it's all based on trust and not on distrust. If I'm there already it's because I trust something there. Because I know exactly what it's about ... For me it's everything needs to be very clear what it is about – transparency ... how do you understand this is indeed neither advertisement but something very serious. Which demands from you some involvement. That's how it can work. So for me it would start here, even before I have any involvement. Then if I am involved then trust is here already.

Or if I have the feeling that it's not clear, what it is about. That it's very vague, and it's not clear, then - it's not that I don't trust, but I think, what is this – pht – not interested ... I think if you cannot for example, if you are not yet ready with the coin, yeah you can tell for the moment we

have this and this finished, but we want to do this and this and this, so it's clear that you have a vision of what will come in the future. I would trust it more I think.

But also if you're thinking about implementing a cryptocurrency, even if it's up in the air, it's still nowadays it's something that a lot of people have difficulties to represent. Maybe the platform can have some tool, maybe in the form of a game, just to understand what it is, because it seems very abstract for a lot of people. And that could be a reason to distrust. Because then like it cannot work - so it's not like I am afraid, or I saw something I don't like, but just I don't trust that this can work. So how do you make this a bit more tangible ... and really implement some form of use, because that platform needs to have users, and that's very different than a platform when you are just getting information. Because you have to be involved. So how can you and how do you start really understanding?

Purpose and clarity were also demonstrated by making only realistic claims and promises:

Unrealistic promises ... then you're like "Oh? Oh? Scam - internet scam."

Trust in the platform was seen as particularly important with the introduction of a digital currency or exchange token:

I was just thinking about ok we are also thinking about creating a cryptocurrency, which is also a common bank ... like I can offer skills in electricity, and another person is interested to buy that service from me, through that circuit, but how I make sure that I also get paid at the end of the thing? ... so how do you check not just the buyer but the whole community of people?

Taken together, these responses suggest that trust in the site itself will depend heavily on the values potential participants ascribe to the site, and their confidence in the site to neither ask for unnecessary data nor exploit the data it does have access to for non-commonfare or commercial purposes. They also suggest that the utility of participating in commonfare.net needs to be evident from the start.

Thus it will be important for the site to present a clear profile and mission statement, and for these to be easily found and digested. The question of user profiles and trust/knowledge which has been exercising the project team for some time seems to apply equally to commonfare.net itself. This is consistent with the notion of commonfare.net as an actor-network as described in Section .3, having an agentic capacity that is separate from those of individual commoners.

Deciding whether to interact with others

Participants were given a set of stickers including 48 suggested items of information that could be included in a commoner's profile plus blanks on which they could write their own suggestions. They were asked to select from these

those that would be needed to decide whether to trust a stranger to interact online. The results of this exercise are critical to WP3, and our attempts to design systems that facilitate the flow of information, knowledge and affect in the commonfare.net assemblage, and hence rely on explicit or implicit trust.

Figure 6: A workshop participant studies the profile information stickers

Items not needed to establish online trust

Of the 48 items included in the stickers, the following were not selected by any participant as important or necessary in establishing trust. Below, we have grouped them into loosely related clusters.

The following items were not selected as important for establishing trust, apparently on the grounds that they were overly-intrusive, personal and not helpful for deciding with whom one wants to interact.

- ▶ Nationality, ethnicity, religion.
- ▶ Gender, sexual orientation, family situation.
- ▶ Age, date of birth.
- ▶ Phone, email, links to physical locations, location, address, places they recommend.
- ▶ Income, contents of digital wallet.

As one participant put it,

Where you live, which is your gender, your sexual preferences, these kind of things. Why do we need that to trust?

And as others pointed out,

... why should we even trust that they're true?

Other items not selected as needed in order to make an interaction with a stranger online likely were:

- ▶ Friendship requests – it is interesting that while most participants indicated a desire to see information about other people’s friendship/trust-networks, no one suggested seeing friendship requests, rather than actual friendship or follower-followee ties. This may suggest that only information about connections that have been in some way “fulfilled” was deemed useful for establishing trustworthiness.

- ▶ Goods for sale – despite the fact that the “skills” item was selected by one participant, no one indicated that they wanted to see “goods for sale” in order to establish trust. This may reflect a desire to establish trust on non-commercial/financial lines, as indicated by the lack of desire to have information about income or digital wallet content.

The final item that was not selected by any participant as necessary to know in establishing trust was:

- ▶ Problems – the fact this was not chosen is consistent with participants’ general desire not to slip into a narrative of “problems and solutions,” i.e. of their lives as a sequence of problems which need resolving, as already noted in earlier research carried out in WP2 and WP3 and reported in D2.1 and D3.1.

I need the basic details, name, picture, but it doesn't have to be accurate. Just something engaging, and a way to communicate ... you know we see that a lot on social media now, people engage with pictures and rarely actual portraits. And somehow it says more.

As demonstrated in the following two quotes from participants, the main things for establishing a basic level of trust in an individual in order to make online interactions more likely were a sense that the person was real, consistent and with an interesting story:

So if you think it's congruent, all the things they tell – ... I can't trust a picture. But if I know something more – for example what that person feels about herself or himself.

In many ways, this is consistent with the desire for the site itself to seem real, consistent and with a clear/engaging purpose.

Items that might be needed to establish trust online

Twenty-six of the 48 items provided were selected by one or more participant as potentially being necessary (or at least useful) in deciding whom to trust. One additional item was put forward as helpful that had not been included in the stickers provided. Again, these have been loosely grouped

Figure 7: Results of the sticker/trust exercise

into themes. In each case, the number of participants selecting that item is given in parentheses.

Items to engage, create congruence, and provide a sense of authenticity

This was the most frequently-occurring category of desired information, and appeared to be about simultaneously engaging interest and establishing a sense that the person with whom one was potentially interacting was authentic, and had a consistent story to tell about themselves.

Despite the widespread sense that personal information could be faked, our workshop participants still felt that they could recognize when a person was presenting a “truthful” narrative. The items selected relating to the creation of an authentic, consistent personal identity were:

- ▶ About (4), personal statement (1)
- ▶ Name (3)
- ▶ Portrait (1), picture (2), avatar (1)
- ▶ Interests (2)
- ▶ Culture preferences (1)
- ▶ Education level (1)
- ▶ Needs (1)

It is important to note that this last item, “needs,” was explicitly related to the desire to establish authenticity rather than as an instrumental matching of a person’s needs with the participant’s own skills/resources:

... for me the most important thing maybe is their needs, because if somebody just puts their skills, and not their needs, then I would be distrusting their skills maybe. Because if someone is honest about their needs, I need to find a job, or I need to communicate with people more, or I yeah I need a platform to actually sell myself, if someone is honest there, then I would get a glimpse of who this person actually is, and that would make me trust them, maybe a little bit more.

Items that assist in establishing whether the other person is part of the same trust assemblage as the respondent

As described above, the WP3 team conceptualize the platform as an assemblage of participants, digital objects and interactions through which information and affect, particularly trust, will flow. Several of the items selected as necessary or desirable for making decisions about whom to trust were in fact related to the question of whether they felt themselves to be part of the same trust assemblage. That is, these items helped the respondents to decide whether they share mutual social connections and overlapping trust histories/groups. This was the second most frequently occurring category of items:

- ▶ People they worked with (4)
- ▶ Friendships (3)
- ▶ Acquaintances (2)
- ▶ Group memberships (2)

- ▶ Groups initiated (1)
- ▶ People they recommend (1)
- ▶ People who follow them (1) – NB this item was not in the stickers provided but was put forward by one of the workshop participants

A sense of belonging to the same trust assemblage was not always enough in its own right, however, to establish a desire to make a connection. Again, emphasising the importance of a sense of authenticity, one participant described how he would combine the personal story with knowledge of mutual acquaintances/friends:

If they give [a] little information, like a story about themselves and I see a picture and it looks like nice person, and their picture is a bit like congruent with that story about themselves, then I think like yeah, I would make contact with them. Most things are like that. For example their skills. It doesn't tell many things but in combination with or for example people they follow, that could be enough for me. If I know the other people, and I trust the other people, then I could trust [this] person.

However, some participants recognized the potential problems with relying on mutual connections:

I suppose that that's a bit of a trap because that's built up over time.

This highlights the importance of making other types of information available, not simply network and friendship connections between people.

Items that assist in establishing individual reliability

The third most frequently occurring category was items that contribute to confidence in the other person’s fulfilling their part of an interaction, whether it be through the provision of a resource, a service, information etc.

- ▶ Good feedback (4)
- ▶ Bad feedback (2)
- ▶ Digital transactions (1)

Feedback was seen as particularly important by several participants:

And you really need the comments, that's why that was my first [choice].

Fewer participants thought being able to see bad feedback a commoner had received was necessary than being able to see good feedback.

These items could be combined with the trust assemblage information described above. As one participant said,

... things for me like their address is meaningless, unless that address is like triple verified by the site, and I've got another reason to trust the site. So all those external details, unless I've got a reason to believe that information, then I wouldn't [think anything of it?]. So you're seeing, which groups they're in, that they have friends in common, and like I say ... so I can see in their history what they do. But the thing of good feedback about them, so I can see if they sell that they're trustworthy. If

it was about selling or sharing or exchanging goods. That they were reliable, that would make a big difference for me.

Items that assist in establishing common interests

While this category is related to the trust-assemblage category above, it is somewhat different in that the items it contains serve to establish common interests (and possibly common values) rather than a pre-existing network of relations through which trust might flow among individuals. As one participant described,

... if I see that the reason they're trying to connect to me is because they're a musician, or because they're working a field that I think ok that's why they're connecting to me. That's why they're putting a hand out, because they see that we've got things in common.

Items falling into this category were:

- ▶ Activities (1)
- ▶ Skills (1)
- ▶ External links website (1)
- ▶ People they follow (1), groups they follow (1)

The last two items are included in this category because they do not imply that the people or groups that the commoner follows have a mutual relationship with them; rather that the commoner follows the person or group because they are interested in their views and/or activities, but that they might be completely unknown to that person or group.

Items relating to communication

Two other items were selected as important in deciding whom to trust. Both of these related to communication, although in rather different ways:

- ▶ The ability to send a direct message
- ▶ Knowledge of a person's language preferences

The first of these is presumably seen as an indicator of someone's openness to being contacted, combined with a desire not to make a first contact in public (this may be especially important if making contacting to set up a transaction of some sort).

In contrast, the second was explained as being a good way to avoid unnecessarily mistrusting someone – if one's preferred and therefore presumably most fluent language is known, it is easier to explain mistakes and find good ways to communicate.

Questions raised

One important question raised in this exercise was the tension between wanting to know about someone's past activities/history and the desire for privacy, and how this relates to the level of trust commoners have in the site itself. For example, while saying that she would be happy for people to see her digital transaction history (because she wanted to be able to see theirs), one participant went on to describe how:

I hate the idea that people can see what books I'm buying, being followed on google, so I would need to feel protected within the site that my information wasn't going outside of that space. And then I'd be open to see what – yeah. To see what I'd bought and sold. If that's what it's about.

Many of the responses to this exercise and the following one on recognition, reward and representation raised the question of moderation and data ownership:

I would say the site shouldn't allow you to erase bad feedback. A moderator maybe but you personally shouldn't be allowed to just erase.

I hate the idea that people can see what books I'm buying, being followed on google, so I would need to feel protected within the site that my information wasn't going outside of that space. And then I'd be open to see what – yeah. To see what I'd bought and sold. If that's what it's about.

Another important question raised during this exercise was the impossibility of separating trust and use:

So I think there is something that is completely entangled, I mean if we're speaking of this kind of plat-form, between trust and use.

Another important question emerging out of this part of the workshop and continuing in the subsequent activity was about hierarchies or levels of trust. Participants felt that the questions, "What do you need to know to trust somebody to make an exchange of goods?" and

"What do you need to know to trust them to communicate?" required different answers.

Participants also emphasised the importance of trust in the platform or in commonfare.net itself in this respect:

And I was just thinking that for example how do you trust that someone so you are willing to actually give up the keys to your place? You trust the platform in the first place.

Recognition, representation and reward

Participants were clear that they thought the commonfare approach was quite different to conventional social networks:

... now what you describe is actually beyond the exchange beyond one person and another, whatever it is service oriented or sell oriented, it's how you belong to a community, actually. That's also very different approach.

Figure 8: The “contributions and reward” exercise

It was evident that what they valued would be contributions that built that community, i.e. ones that strengthened and sustained the commonfare assemblage.

Recognizing and representing contributions to the commonfare.net assemblage

Participants were asked whether they would like information about their contributions to the creation and growth of the commonfare assemblage to be visible to other commoners.

There were several reasons given for wanting others to be able to see information about your contributions to commonfare.net:

- ▶ It is a good way to see how active a person is on the platform and in what way (builds trust).
- ▶ One should be able to choose if visible or not – or – the site needs to set the structure (inclined to think all contributions should be public).
- ▶ So my contribution can be challenged, discussed.
- ▶ Because this would impel others to get involved.
- ▶ Sharing knowledge – degree of engagement.
- ▶ Interest of my questions (many people who ask the same question) – external validation.
- ▶ Exchanging knowledge/services – degree of participation.
- ▶ Reactions to my answers – external validation.

In particular, the idea that visible information about contributions could help both determine the value of one’s contributions and build trust seemed important. Participants wanted to be able to ‘show to others my degree of engagement’:

... it’s a good way to see how active a person is on the platform, and in what way, and I think that builds trust. If someone is just asking a lot of questions and it’s annoying questions then I don’t necessarily trust them. But if they’re also exchanging goods and sharing other things then someone is very active and I might be inclined to trust them a lot more.

An additional reason was that publicity might increase other people’s involvement and so help to enrol others as actants in the commonfare assemblage rather than as passive nodes in a network:

So yes, I would like showing my contribution ... I was just thinking what if I want to initiate a group of patrons, that they actually come together, put some money, and then can [offer] some form of grants, I mean I just was trying to think a bit about what this contribution is about, it’s not necessarily about asking questions or answering questions it maybe initiating something in the platform. So you want it to be public because you need others.

Some participants felt that the visibility of their contributions/contribution history should be a matter of choice and/or context, ‘preserving the right to privacy when it seems appropriate’:

... would you like others to be able to see information about your contribution, I think should be yes or no. It depends if you want to be visible in that situation or not ... Then you need to decide, perhaps sometimes yes I am proud of this and I want to share it, also we are proud of the things we do, but other times perhaps you say no we keep it – privacy is also a necessity.

However, the same participant also recognized a tension between the ideal of individual choice and the possible

reality of chaos:

But I'm more inclined to a structure which the website decide and set up a pre-condition, I'm not really, because of personal experience in these non-hierarchical quite utopian ways, usually it just bureaucratic nightmare. And sometimes the structure is made ... you all agree to certain conditions. In that visibility should be put by the structure itself. But in my other personality we should be able to decide.

Participants had various ideas relating to the ways in which contributions might be represented.

Some wanted information about the amount of every kind of contribution to be made visible, including the number of links they had shared and the number of posts they contributed, perhaps like the information available about contributions to StackOverflow.

One suggestion was a "contribution page," presumably part of the commoner profile, with subgroups of contributions made by that commoner, so that s/he could also see what kind of contributions s/he hadn't yet made:

I think it would inspire me to contribute to more in more areas, if I see that there are different areas to contribute to.

The other piece of contribution history that participants wanted to be made visible was reviews the commoner had received from others.

Participants were generally agreed that a four or five star scale representation, as commonly used in conventional reputation systems, would not be appropriate for recognising and showing contributions to commonfare.net:

... my degree of participation, actually. So not like stars ... it's not ... how many stars I've got, but how engaged I am, how motivated I am.

In fact, the general feeling was that star-based ratings/visualizations should be avoided, as evident in the following exchange:

P1: It's quite a lot to do with the army, actually.

P2: That's a reason to distrust, by the way.

Rewards for contributions to the commonfare assemblage

Participants had some interesting things to say about whether their contributions to the strength and sustainability of the commonfare assemblage should be linked to rewards. Even before the question of rewards was explicitly raised with them, participants raised both affective rewards (people saying good things about them, 'lots of hugs and kisses') and

practical rewards ('some store of value that you can use').

Those that were open to some kind of reward system raised a variety of issues:

- ▶ Things that you are asked to do by others.
- ▶ Maybe the ones that take me a lot of time and effort.
- ▶ Voluntarily.
- ▶ Mutual agreement.
- ▶ Some exchange of value for direct provision of concrete services.
- ▶ Maybe not rewarded but "redirected", "curated" (by whom?).
- ▶ Because it motivates me to contribute more.

Others saw the intrinsic rewards as equally or more important:

... some exchange of value for direct provision of concrete services, [but] the reward is in the exchange and the commonality, i.e. connection is the reward and ... the sense of mutual generosity.

Some participants felt that extrinsic rewards were only appropriate in some circumstances:

... the things that have taken me a lot of time and effort, or things that you were asked to do by others. If I post a question or I volunteer a tutorial, I don't need to be rewarded for it, it's something I want to share.

On the question of what form rewards should take, participants had a range of suggestions, including some additional access to common assets, for example a pool of donated goods.

One suggestion which was extremely popular with the whole group was the idea of 'favour points,' tokens that meant that 'at some stage you can ask for one back.' This suggestion already hints at the potential uses of the proposed digital currency.

It was important to participants that any reward system should be negotiated and decided within the community, but that once it was in place all users should agree to commit to the same system.

They also raised important questions, such as whether a reward system was actually crucial to foster involvement in commonfare.net, and who, in fact, does the rewarding:

... how does it work so it's not top-down? But at the same time it really defines what the platform is. And that has to come from within. You could imagine if at some point there was I dunno, a bit like Wikipedia may work. You

have a committee of people who are ... discussing what's going in and out. [Not to determine what is true/correct] but if it's about a reward, what should be emphasised and why, and when, and who decides, and how can that be a shared decision process?

Finally, on the question of whether rewards, as well as contributions, should be visible to others, feelings were divided.

Some felt that making rewards visible would provide further evidence of commitment and trustworthiness, in addition to a contribution history and reviews from other commoners. It was also suggested that having visible rewards would be an illustration of the site's values, helping to develop the clarity of purpose and ethos identified as so desirable above.

Most, however, did not want information on rewards to be public. They felt that a visualization or other representation of contributions would be enough, and information on rewards should remain private. The two primary reasons given for reward privacy are illustrated in the following quotes:

Oh no, no. Privacy ... it's interesting ... for other people to see my contributions and to see a bit the quality but not my what my rewards are ... I would not like them to see, [I have] so many coins.

... because if my contributions are public then my rewards don't need to be, and if I choose to do some-thing without a reward, then I don't want it to obligate me to do it for free again if someone asks me. Because I have a really big problem with putting a price on myself, so I might do one of you a favour because I know you, and then someone will see oh, she did this for free, so she can do it for free for me as well.

3.3.3 Initial findings from the Commonpoly game

Early findings on the needs of potential commoners with respect to the currency design came from workshops and focus groups held by the WP2 partners, particularly in the Netherlands and Croatia as part of the initial research for D2.1 and subsequent on-going engagement and co-design activities. According to our pilot partners (BIN-Italia, CPS and Museu da Crise, 2017), these included the following desirable features:

- ▶ Transparency
- ▶ High level of flexibility
- ▶ Autonomy to create own currency, self-determination, independence – but also inter-exchangeable currencies.
- ▶ Community-based money systems including the sharing of any potential profits and losses, and mutual or community funds.
- ▶ The possibility to use the currency in the offline world.

Equally important were undesirable features:

- ▶ Debts, hoarding, accumulation and interest rates.
- ▶ Speculation, particularly being able to invest in things

that are detrimental to the commonfare.

- ▶ Any form of taxation, or anything that reminds commoners of austerity policies.

They also included suggestions to consider the possibility of creating time/event-based and location-based currencies.

Based on these initial findings, Museu da Crise have designed a game, Commonpoly, which they have started to use to get input from potential commoners into the design of the digital currency/currencies. The process through which this input is acquired is through observation of the rules created for the game, which players determine in a cooperative, consensus approach.

The main findings from the first two play-throughs of the game, both conducted with groups of freelancers in Amsterdam in August 2017, are:

- ▶ Even though not prompted to do so, players introduced a basic income early in the game, but one that was conditional in that it was only to be paid to those with insufficient income. This was to avoid depleting finite funds.
- ▶ Players decided it is necessary to have a Common Fund for the game community. On commonfare.net, this might translate to common funds for specific groups and sub-communities.
- ▶ Players felt that, with the Community Fund established, there was no need for a bank.
- ▶ Players decided that the content of digital wallets should be shown to everyone. This is particularly interesting given that the same group of freelancers mostly did not want their rewards for contributions to the commonfare to be made visible (see previous section).
- ▶ Players wanted a limited amount of money supply, perhaps increasing in proportion to the number of participants.
- ▶ Players decided to place a cap on the amount of coins any one person could have above the amount needed to “live comfortably.” Especially in the second game, it was stressed that it is very important to dignity and happiness to be able to have more than the minimum required to meet absolutely basic needs.
- ▶ In order to maintain the value of the commonfare, it was decided that unused coins should be put back into circulation over time.
- ▶ A strong feeling emerged that debt should not be possible in the system, and so there is no need for a negative balance.
- ▶ There was a desire to have a paper or physical representation of the (digital) coin.
- ▶ On the question of whether players should be able to introduce their own coin, no clear consensus was reached.

3.4 SUMMARY AND IMPLICATIONS

Taken together, the main design considerations for WP3 emerging from the research reported in D2.1 (Fumagalli et al., 2017), D3.1 (Wilson et al., 2017) and the more recent research described in Section 3.3 above can be summarized as follows.

Although the pilot sites are engaging different demographic groups, there are some important commonalities both in terms of experiences and values.

The majority report negative experiences of relations with the State and the capitalist/commercial world of work. This includes loss of control, exploitation, and a reduction in dignity. The currency and social dynamics components/systems on commonfare.net (plus the broader site itself) need to be designed to ensure that commoners' sense of dignity and self-authorship is not further eroded by their interactions and experiences on the platform.

Related to this, the majority described low levels of trust in large-scale technological platforms/corporations such as Facebook and Google. Particularly resented is a sense of loss of control over one's own data and one's interactions with the platform/system. Commonfare.net system design needs to acknowledge this, and work towards ensuring that commoners feel they have control over (and input into) the way the platform uses their platform interaction data.

For many, precarity is hidden or unacknowledged by the State due to the increasing prevalence of personal indebtedness, and in fact State actions tend to exacerbate people's situations. This means that the components/systems of commonfare.net that have a quantitative representation, such as measurements of contribution, trust, or currency, need to avoid adding to a debt culture by allowing people to build up deficits. Currency design might also be explicitly used to target real-world debt.

Many people experiencing precarity find themselves relatively isolated, wither because they cannot afford to socialize or because they no longer have any free time (or both). Systems on commonfare.net need to be designed to help people find others they might wish to interact with, to develop trust in them, and to feel they are part of a community that they contribute to as well as that they may receive something from.

While new forms of solidarity are emerging that contribute to a form of commonfare, the commonality is limited – that is, mutuality and cooperation may be restricted to groups of like-minded people of similar age and background. Thus components/systems of commonfare.net that analyse network dynamics and recognize/reward positive contributions may need to identify situations in which cliques or barriers are forming, and perhaps break them down by targeted information diffusion. It will be particularly important to ensure that components intended to facilitate trust are recognized and understood equally across a variety of different groups.

These general considerations lead on to more targeted issues relating to trust, recognition/reward, and the circulation of digital currencies.

Summarizing the main findings from the two workshops on

trust and recognition/reward, we found that the following factors were particularly important to participants:

- ▶ Emphasis on the ethos and values of the site itself;
- ▶ Balance between issues of trust and issues of practical use-value;
- ▶ Distaste for conventional ratings system but desire to have some visible comments and history information as a measure of contribution and commitment;
- ▶ Related to this, a strong sentiment that trust is built up through a person's consistent, coherent behaviour that displays values you share; and
- ▶ Mixed feelings about extrinsic reward, and a sense that any reward system should be negotiated among the commoners.

These findings echoed those already reported in D3.1 (Wilson et al., 2017) but provided more detailed information on potential commoners' feelings and opinions. They suggest that systems that recognize and represent positive contributions to the creation of the commonfare will be valued, but (because of the potential for depression, a feeling of loss of control and anxiety described in D3.1 and above) they will have to be designed sensitively, so that commoners do not feel that they are being judged and found wanting by or compared to others. They also suggest that questions as to whether contribution should be linked to concrete reward require more and perhaps ongoing input from commoners, as the platform and its systems will belong to them.

Finally, in relation to the digital currency, key issues again appear to be trust, transparency, and autonomy, and features to avoid include debts, hoarding, interest rates, accumulation and the kind of conditionality associated with State provisions, such as the Dutch Social Support (or Participation) Act (see, for example, Lub and Uytterlinde, 2012). Potential commoners seemed open to the idea of a basic income, but more co-design efforts are needed to understand what form it should take in the different pilot contexts and to what extent it should be unconditional and universal.

While the findings presented in this section are important input into the currency design and approaches to trust, contribution-recognition and reward, the WP3 team has also had to bear in mind that much of the most recent research, targeted explicitly on trust, contribution-recognition, reward and currency, come from a single subsection of the target groups – precarious freelancers – and that their ideas may not be replicated in subsequent workshops and play-throughs of Commonpoly with other target groups (non-Western migrants, young unemployed and benefit recipients). However, they do have the advantage that freelancers are represented across all the pilot sites, with precarious workers in the arts and entertainment playing an important role in piloting the digital currency in Milan (see D3.1), and some precarious freelancers being involved in the research undertaken in Croatia for D3.1.

The following chapter describes the proposals that the WP3 team are putting forward in response to both the conceptual and empirical contexts described in this and the previous chapter.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS ARISING

This chapter presents concrete proposals relating to the digital currency, trust, contribution-recognition and reward, and platform misuse detection systems introduced in Chapter 2.

Section 4.1 presents proposals for the implementation of complementary digital currencies on commonfare.net in the form of cryptographically secured digital value tokens. Section 4.1.1 compares three alternative systems.

Section 4.2 proposes the integration of dynamic network analysis and contribution, trust and reward systems. Section 4.2.1 introduces the novel concept of a contribution-measuring system based on the calculation of network metrics and resulting in a quantitative indicator or recognition of contribution. In the context of commonfare.net, we call this indicator a commoner's **commonshare**. Section 4.2.2 considers how commonshare values can be used to increase the effectiveness of information diffusion. Section 4.2.3 describes ways in which a visible indicator of a commoner's commonshare might be combined with more conventional indicators of behaviour, such as reviews from other commoners, in order to facilitate trust. Section 4.2.4 puts forward ways in which contribution to the commonfare might be rewarded through an augmentation of the basic income that is at the heart of the commonfare approach to welfare provision. Finally, Section 4.2.5 proposes ways in which dynamic network analysis metrics could be used to detect and flag up collusion to the system administrators.

4.1 DIGITAL CURRENCY ON COMMONFARE.NET

As described in Section 2.2, one of the key elements of the commonfare.net platform is the implementation of one or more cryptographically-secured digital value tokens. The project proposal included use of digital currency or value tokens for three purposes: to facilitate the exchange of goods, services and skills; to provision an unconditional, universal basic income within the platform; and to offer a means of rewarding positive contributions to the platform and so to the building of the commonfare.

The following sections present the digital currency options open to the project at present.

4.1.1 The three options for the digital currency on commonfare.net: Faircoin2, the Yetta Protocol and Commoncoin

This section presents three alternative digital currency solutions for commonfare.net. They are the result of more than one year of research in the field of distributed ledgers technology, conducted by Dyne.org, with the aim of exploring options from which the consortium may choose a solution for the pilots in 2018.

The first solution described is the adoption of Faircoin2, a complementary digital value token for the global cooperative movement. The second alternative is the Yetta Protocol, an open source blockchain protocol for philanthropist-sponsored initiatives such as basic income, funding of scholarships and internships and economic development, using a complementary currency or digital value token. The final option is a combination of philanthropist-sponsored initiatives and a commonfare.net-specific, non-convertible complementary digital value token, to be exchanged by commoners on the platform. In such a combined system, commonfare.net would offer both Commoncoin – a complementary currency in the form of a digital value token to use exclusively on the commonfare.net platform – and a smart contract provisioning for philanthropy-funded basic income, with social innovations made for social contributions to be included in the smart contracts. The latter are to be intended as socio-technical possibilities, whereby a cryptographically secured digital value token could be piloted to be exchangeable in euros as a form of donation. After presentation of each of the three possible alternatives in the three subsections below, a comparative analysis is provided in Table 1.

Both Faircoin2 and Commoncoin can be seen as experiments to be tested in a controlled environment within the pilot communities. However, the Yetta Protocol may have the potential to be a scalable and long-term sustainable digital currency solution for commonfare.net, should its Initial Coin Offering (planned for late 2017) and ongoing model

prove successful. It is the strong conviction of Dyne.org - the project partner in charge of the research and design of the digital currency system for commonfare.net - that the option finally chosen by the project consortium should be the one that can most effectively address the needs of people experiencing precarious financial and/or employment conditions.

Faircoin2

Faircoin2 is the first candidate for the digital currency system on commonfare.net that Dyne.org considered. It is a complementary digital value token secured that can be used both within and outwith the commonfare.net platform. It may be an appropriate currency for the platform for three main reasons. First, it is a currency in which the underlying consensus algorithm is aligned with the cooperative values that also underpin the commonfare.net ethos. This is contrary to the majority of cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin. Second, the pilot community at Macao in Italy was already familiar with this system, even before the beginning of the current project, and this pointed to the possibility to adapt it to the contexts of the Croatian and Dutch pilots. Third, Dyne.org already collaborates with the Faircoin2 community and the latter was keen to support the pilots in commonfare.net

Faircoin was initially launched in 2014 by Integral Cooperative of Catalunya as a mix of Proof-of-Work and Proof-of-Stake consensus algorithms to authenticate transactions in a distributed ledger. According to the Faircoin website:

FairCoin is the first fairly distributed crypto currency. 99.99% Proof-Of-Stake, FairCoin rewards savers. All the coins were pre-mined and fairly distributed to thousands of people from all over the world. Backed by a strong, diverse and committed community. Promotes prosperity and financial freedom with real value. Working to become the coin of fair trade. Faircoin is the first project where the coins are not bought but rather distributed equally between everyone who wants them regardless of their current financial status, and promotes equality.

(<http://fair-coin.org>)

Indeed, unlike Bitcoin, and to be more environmentally friendly, faircoins have been created, or pre-mined, within the genesis block. Faircoin is based on a different proof for reaching decentralized consensus validation of transactions on its ledger: Proof-of-Stake rather than Proof-of-Work as for Bitcoin (Nakamoto, 2008). In this case, transactions are validated on the basis of how much hard-drive memory a participant in the network shares with the network as whole, rather than on the basis of CPU and GPU clock cycles to find strings that the algorithm assigns in an aleatory fashion as for Bitcoin.

Faircoin has been reintroduced in 2017 as Faircoin2, presented as the first 100% cooperative blockchain based on Proof-of-Cooperation (König and Duran, 2016). At the operational level, in the case of Faircoin2, the cryptocurrency supply has been pre-mined. In this way, the value of this complementary digital value token is meant to grow against the value of other tokens traded on exchanges as organizers

foresee increasing adoption.

The functioning of the Proof-of-Cooperation consensus algorithm can be summarized as follows. As a node is certified by Faircoin2 developers, essentially by identifying the node operator through personal contact and verification, each Certified Validation Node simply verifies the new block by following a chronological order without making machines work just to find the new block. In practice, the machines that are in charge of finding and validating the transactions do it in a rotating form by signing them with the Schnorr signature protocol (Schnorr 1991). They receive a small reward for their cooperation and for the minimum amount of energy that they use. In other words, Certified Validation Nodes operate as it happens for minters in a Proof-of-Stake environment, earning a small fee to support the operations of the network. However, validators are rewarded not as a result of competitive behaviour, but to reflect the recognition by all that they serve the community. As stated on the Faircoin website,

The big difference in FairCoin compared to other crypto currencies is that we introduce a certain level of trust and democratic values even on the technical level. FairCoin is not trust-less in terms of block creation, but trust-less in terms of transactions.

(<https://fair-coin.org/en/faircoin-faqs>)

This ethos of communal, cooperative operation aligns well with the underlying philosophy of the commonfare approach (described in Chapter 2) and the resulting design principles for commonfare.net.

However, there are reasons to consider alternatives to Faircoin2. Indeed, from the technical and currency design standpoints, Faircoin2 has some possible drawbacks. While it may be that individuals and groups of potential commoners brought into the project through direct contact with pilot partners will be amenable to its adoption, Faircoin2 may lack potential scalability as the community of commoners grows and especially after the completion of the project in June 2019. In fact, Faircoin has only been adopted by a few thousand users since its inception almost four years ago. Moreover, it is not clear at this stage whether commoners would buy Faircoins after the pilot phase in which faircoins will be offered by Dyne.org. Although it is too early to judge how it will go with Faircoin2, the lack of mainstream acceptance of Faircoin signals a potential need to look for alternatives; if commonfare.net adopts a digital currency solution that the majority of people are unwilling to use, that will cause major problems for its long-term sustainability. On the other hand, it may be that using Faircoin2 in commonfare.net may lead precisely to the increase in uptake that would eventually lead to more familiarity for potential users and therefore to the possibility of a domino effect of increased adoption.

The Yetta Protocol

The second proposal considered by Dyne.org as a candidate to become the digital currency solution for commonfare.net is the Yetta Protocol¹ (Hubbard and Sachy, 2017). This distributed ledger protocol has been co-designed by Marco

¹for a detailed description of its possible application to the commonfare.net pilots, please see the Yetta White Paper.

Sachy and Darrell Hubbard. The former is the currency designer for commonfare.net from Dyne.org while the latter is an accomplished computer scientist. Darrell Hubbard contacted Marco Sachy in June 2017, offering his help and experience in the design of a scalable and long-term sustainable digital currency system for the PIE News project. Following their collaborative work on the Yetta Protocol, Marco Sachy is now also Chief Digital Officer with the Yetta Foundation representing the interests of Commonfare pilots on its Board.

The idea underpinning the design of the Yetta Protocol is to leverage prosocial spending for basic income purposes. According to Aknin et al. (2013),

... human beings around the world derive emotional benefits from using their financial resources to help others. [...] Survey data from 136 countries were examined and showed that prosocial spending is associated with greater happiness around the world, in poor and rich countries alike. [Such] findings suggest that the reward experienced from helping others may be deeply ingrained in human nature, emerging in diverse cultural and economic contexts.

(Aknin et. al., 2013, p635)

The idea to leverage prosocial spending to provide basic income has already been successfully applied in less developed countries with projects such as GiveDirectly, whereby donors provision unconditional basic income in cash on a monthly basis to people in Kenya and Uganda. GiveDirectly has raised circa US\$30 million since 2012 (<http://givedirectly.org/>). Within the crypto industry,

projects such as the Initial Coin Offering for the Seratio Token by the UK-based Centre for Citizenship Enterprise and Governance (<http://www.cceg.org.uk/>) show that distributed ledger technologies, and in particular smart contracts in the form of cryptographically-secured digital value tokens, are increasingly being seen as a means to achieve bottom-up economic development. As the organizers of this first Initial Coin Offering within the UK regulatory framework, which will begin on 1st October 2017, put it:

The unique feature of the Seratio token is the ability to capture the financial assets, microshares and provenance of transactions involving people, products, processes, projects and organizations.

(<https://www.seratio-coins.world/index.html>)

With the Yetta Protocol, the rationale is to implement an initiative based on philanthropic donations to provide basic income by exploiting the features of Initial Coin Offerings to issue complementary digital value tokens, cryptographically secured to achieve such an end. Indeed, the Yetta Token adds an economic reward to prosocial spending, thus increasing the incentive to help others as yetta is a token designed as a tool for mutual self-reinforcing economic development of the global community. We are hopeful that this model will be successful because philanthropy is already a multi-trillion dollar industry worldwide (Mintz, 2015).

In practice, the Yetta Protocol is an open source protocol for interoperable smart contracts. A smart contract is a self-executing computerized transaction protocol that automatically implements the terms of an agreement

Figure 9: Yetta Protocol smart contract offerings (SOURCE: graph designed and courtesy of Darrell Hubbard, 2017)

between parties while minimizing the need for trusted intermediaries. Within the commonfare.net context, there would be the potential option to pilot in a research environment a series of smart contracts designed and prototyped to meet the needs of the pilot communities as they emerged during the research published in D.2.1, D3.1 and Chapter 3 of this document.

The commonfare.net pilot communities will have the possibility to use a complementary digital cryptographically-secured value token called yetta (as it would be by adopting Faircoin2). Furthermore, they will also be able to access monetary resources in fiat currency, i.e. the euro, as the protocol is a backend that can automate both the flow of digital currency and reputation dynamics in an ecosystem whereby precarious financial and employment conditions can be tackled systemically. The Yetta Protocol is the technological enabler of a highly innovative way to approach sustainable economic development.

The Yetta Protocol smart contracts will operate differently to traditional donation models: in the yetta approach, contributions will be paid directly to individuals as a form of basic income, instead of to the non-profit or charitable organization where the majority of donations may end up allocated to general overheads. In the yetta model, contributions will be made available to the social, civic, or higher education institution. However, these contributions can only be withdrawn through an individual basic income, educational, or employment smart contract. Thus funding is allocated at the level of the organization, but disbursed at the level of the individual.

In the commonfare.net context, for example, philanthropists could purchase Yetta Tokens in fiat currency (for instance euro,) and the latter could be sent to pilot participants experiencing poverty, precarity or exclusion. In turn, these pilot participants could either keep Yetta Tokens or convert them to fiat money (for instance the euro).

An overview of the core Smart Contracts offered by the Yetta Protocol is presented in Figure 9.

The Yetta Protocol adopts a CORE, Common, and Unique smart contracts development framework to ensure ubiquity and scalability across current and future blockchain development. Yetta CORE represents smart contracts that are accessible across all industry or market sectors within our ecosystem, such as token purchases, and transfer of value functionality. Yetta Common represents a group of smart contracts specific to an industry or market sector, such as educational and workforce development smart contracts. Yetta Unique would represent extensions to the Yetta CORE and Common code set to provide additional functionality needed within a specific organization. A visual representation of Yetta Protocol smart contracts development framework is provided in Figure 9. For a depiction of the Yetta Protocol applied to the philanthropic ecosystem see Figure 10.

In the context of basic income provision in fiat currency on commonfare.net, the Yetta Protocol could provide two classes of basic income smart contracts – unconditional basic income and philanthropic basic income. Both classes of basic income would be provisioned by converting yetta

Figure 10: The yetta philanthropic ecosystem (SOURCE: graph designed and courtesy of Darrell Hubbard, 2017)

complementary digital value tokens (i.e. Yetta Tokens) into euros, the latter acquired through philanthropic donations.

In addition, the Yetta Protocol could be used in the commonfare.net context to try to generate new opportunities for employment. For example, the majority of NGOs are underfunded and could benefit from an infusion of qualified labour to advance their social missions and goals. The unemployed, whether educated or uneducated, could fulfil many of the labour and skilled roles needed within the NGO community. Thus one of the goals that the philanthropist-investor approach hopes to achieve is the creation of jobs and reduction of unemployment while simultaneously satisfying the human capital needs of NGOs.

Finally, the Yetta Protocol could be applied to support precarious students in both higher and vocational education by funding either their scholarships or education institutions directly. This would reward the education institution with funding, the economically disadvantaged prospective students with a scholarship or new graduates with paid internships, and the philanthropist with a digital and highly liquid store of value in the form of a complementary digital value token. In sum, the Yetta Protocol has the potential to offer a complementary digital currency system for commonfare.net with good possibilities to explore around both scalability and long-term sustainability.

A dual system: Commoncoin and basic income in euros

As demonstrated with the analysis of the Macao case study in D3.1, it is possible to blend the features of a complementary and non-convertible digital value token to be exclusively used on the commonfare.net platform with the provision of a basic income in fiat money coming from the conversion of complementary value tokens into euros. In the Yetta Token case, this basic income would be sourced from philanthropic donations. Thus a third option for the digital currency system on commonfare.net is the adoption of a dual currency system (both non-convertible and convertible complementary digital value smart tokens) similar to that in operation for the Macao collective, but developed and generalized to accommodate the needs of all pilots.

The desire for a complementary digital value smart token that is autonomous and independent of fiat currencies is both consistent with the commonfare approach and aligned with the desires of potential commoners described in Chapter 3. In practice, it is possible to envision a digital currency system whereby those registering on commonfare.net would receive both a complementary and a non-convertible digital value smart token (named Commoncoin) to exchange services with others exclusively on the platform. Furthermore, this solution could provide a source of basic income in euros coming from the dynamics of the philanthropic Yetta Protocol described in the previous section. It could also potentially be used in the distribution of complementary digital value smart tokens as rewards for contribution to the commonfare, through the commonshare dynamics (described in Section 4.2.4).

In this case, basic income could be provisioned in euros from as it happens for the Macao collective, because the Yetta Protocol would simply offer, with blockchain technology, a way to put in touch donors and recipients in a horizontal, peer-to-peer fashion mediated by smart contracts. The main difference with Macao would be scale, as the adoption of the Yetta Protocol would allow commoners to tap into fiat money donations through convertible complementary digital value smart tokens (the latter to be converted into fiat money). If the launch of the Yetta Token and continued investment in it proves successful, this could be several orders of magnitude higher in volume if compared to the revenue produced at Macao through events sold to the external public and paid for in euros.

In particular, by implementing philanthropic basic income smart contracts, people experiencing precarious financial and employment conditions would enjoy a philanthropist-sponsored basic income donations, similar to welfare. Philanthropic donations would be intended to provision basic income to the recipients. Yet, disbursements would be

allocated on an individual basis as donations. As an example of this approach, see givedirectly.org (<http://givedirectly.org>). In other words, philanthropists could contribute to a basic income for a country's population based upon a percentage of their current-value (or speculative-value increase) in yetta complementary digital value smart tokens. This raises another difference compared to the experience to date in the Italian pilot, in that the Macao collective raises money for its continued function by selling events and services to the public, rather than through explicitly prosocial spending. Thus while increasing the potential scale and sustainability of basic income generation, this model has a somewhat different power dynamic compared to that at Macao, which may not be welcomed by the commoners who seek autonomy and self-authorship (see Chapter 3).

This third option of a dual currency or digital value token system is essentially an extension of the Yetta Protocol solution described in the previous section. On the one hand, the Yetta Protocol can provide a digital value smart token, yetta, together with smart contracts to provision basic income in euros. This could allow for forms of debt relief and income generation in both fiat money and digital value smart tokens, provisioned through philanthropic donations. However, the Yetta Protocol can also allow the generation of complementary digital value smart tokens backed by yetta, so it would be possible to create a Commoncoin that would not be exchangeable for either fiat money or other cryptocurrencies on crypto exchanges, in order to prevent leaks of value from the commonfare.net platform. This choice would structurally avoid Commoncoin being prone to speculative dynamics, but would make it less effective in providing debt relief and income availability.

Comparison of the three digital currency systems

The three possibilities for digital currencies within commonfare.net described above are summarized in Table 1.

CURRENCY SYSTEM SOLUTION	DEBT RELIEF AND POSSIBILITY FOR INCOME GENERATION	CONTROL OVER CURRENCY SUPPLY	GOVERNANCE	CONVERTIBILITY	SCALABILITY AND LONGTERM SUSTAINABILITY
Faircoin2	Low	Since Faircoin comes pre-minted, the supply is already set up and there is no possibility for control.	Dependant on Faircoin2 core team choice	Possible, but prone to low demand as for the past 3 years	Low
Yetta Protocol	High	High and adjustable as it can be set up according to platform needs	Governance by users through voting	Possible, potentially more valuable as Yetta Token could see higher demand than Faircoin2 because of its philanthropic model	High
Commoncoin	High	High and adjustable as it can be set up according to platform needs	Governance by users through voting	Not possible as design choice	High

Table 1: Comparison of the three digital currency options presented in this deliverable

All three systems are in principle suitable for use in the commonfare.net context, but if compared to Faircoin the Yetta Protocol, perhaps together with Commoncoin, could potentially do so in a more effective way, in a shorter period of time and meeting the economic needs of more people. From an objective and neutral point of view, one should notice that the supply of faircoins, after an initial donation by Dyne.org, would be prone to the disposable income that commoners active on the platform could invest to buy more faircoins. Alternatively, participants to commonfare.net would need to negotiate with Faircoin organizers in order to acquire more coins from them. This would not be the case with yetta and commoncoins, because the latter two would be supplied directly to the platform without prior investment from pilot participants and those willing to participate after the pilot phase would be endowed with voting powers to deliberate in a bottom-up fashion on the governance of both yetta and commoncoin systems.

Furthermore, although the ethos and the plan to leverage ethical banking to boost impact promoted by Faircoin2 is legitimate and desirable, the Yetta Protocol – either as Yetta Token or as the basis for the Commoncoin system – could perhaps more effectively tackle financial and employment precarity in that it would embed a reward for philanthropy which may be a more powerful self-reinforcing mechanism for adoption and scale. Such considerations do not apply to commoncoin if taken as a non-convertible complementary digital value token, while they would in the case where Commoncoin as a system was applied also by implementing yetta smart contracts, ultimately convertible into donations in euros.

Notwithstanding such qualitative differences among the three digital currency systems described above, this comparative analysis has been conducted for research purposes and without the delivery partner (Dyne.org) recommending one option over another. Instead, the PIE News consortium as a whole will make an educated decision on the solution to adopt for the pilots.

4.2 RECOGNIZING AND MEASURING CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE COMMONFARE

As described in Section 2.3, the following proposals for integrating Dynamic Network Analysis and contribution-recognition, trust and reward systems are underpinned by an assemblage conceptualization of commonfare.net. In this, actants in the assemblage (or nodes in the network) contribute to its strength and value through their interactions.

Fundamental principles of our thinking include that commonfare.net is both constituted by and belongs to the commoners; and its value is created by the connections and interactions between commoners and the resources that will come to populate the platform. Value (common good) is created in all interactions, including those in which a commoner asks for advice, guidance or material help, and is not limited to contributions where someone answers a question or provides a solution.

As is evident from the empirical research described in Chapter 3, potential commoners seem to feel that their contribution and commitment to the platform should be recognized in some way. This leads us to the idea that each commoner creates and owns a share of the common value being created through those interactions. Henceforth, we refer to this share as a commoner's **commonshare**. The following sections suggest a way in which this commonshare can be calculated, and then ways in which it can be put to use to help sustain, grow and protect the commonfare assemblage.

4.2.1 Calculating the commonshare

From the WP3 standpoint, commonfare.net is a social network platform where user interactions are mediated by contents, and such contents are stories, discussion forum posts, postings describing goods, skills or services, profile pages for individuals or groups, and so on. To help us understand this, we need to define a suitable temporal graph dynamics to capture the evolution of relations unfolding on the platform. The dynamic model represents a variation of the baseline graph model presented in Sec. 2.3. The goal of this graph model is twofold:

1. It should capture the dynamics by which the commonfare.net community creates and accesses the common wealth of contents shared online.
2. It should track how interactions among commoners and contents are engendered.

A dynamic graph model is a standard way to capture the emergence of aggregated complex dynamics. It is defined based on local interactions at the user level, e.g., atomic actions such as creating and sharing a content, making a comment on a content or replying to such a comment.

As far as the software platform is concerned, log traces will permit the reconstruction of temporal information about the visualization of a certain content by a commoner (with a click-through mechanisms) and interactions among commoners. In practice, the platform can record the logs of all accesses to specific contents. In Release 2 of commonfare.net, due at the time of submission of this document, the digital contents will be profiles and stories, which are planned to be visible by default to all commoners. Commoners can therefore interact through comments on contents they view. Hence, we are interested in the evolution of the relation between agents of the platform and new stories (both actants in the assemblage) which appear over time. In this case, interactions among commoners would be traced by recording if/how they react to specific stories, e.g., either directly addressing the content owner or discussing with other commoners about the specific content. The same ideas and methods can be extended and generalized to interactions with other digital content; for the purposes of the following discussion, we take interactions with stories as the illustrative example, since these will be possible even from Release 2 and therefore such data will be rapidly available for experimentation in the remainder of the project.

The way that commoners access the contents and participate in the platform storytelling process is twofold. As

described in D3.1, stories to be shared can be either created by the platform administrator, or can be user-generated. We recommend the following platform features, which we can then leverage on for the dynamic network analysis.

- ▶ Every story should have a timeline composed of commoners' comments, and the owner of a content is notified of comments on it from others.
- ▶ Every commoner has her own timeline where she can receive recommendations to specific stories;
- ▶ Every new story posted by a certain commoner is recommended to all of his friends, i.e., commoners connected to them, i.e., those who have a link with them (see below). Commoners can also recommend other stories to their friends.

We can track at each point in time two types of dynamic relations, and construct the union of the resulting two graphs.

Links between contents and commoners: when commoners access a content, they create a connection to the specific content. Models which capture the creation of relations between users and contents have been proposed for standard commercial platforms. Diaz, Porter and Onnela (2010) studied an evolving graph model where rewiring and attachment define the evolution of a bipartite network. In that model, the edges connect users and catalogues of videos. In Release 2 of the commonfare.net platform, contents are the stories appearing in the platform. In subsequent releases, other types of content will be available for interactions.

Links between commoners: commoners who comment on a given content or reply to other commoners' comments on a given content establish an interaction with the owner of the content or with those who made a comment. This requires a richer graph model compared to the standard catalogue model used by Diaz, Porter and Onnela (2010), and we can capture from the logs the interaction of commoners mediated by the contents' discussion.

The evolution of the commonfare.net assemblage can be modelled using an evolving graph in the following manner.

We start considering two sets of nodes. The first set is the set of the contents, and the second set is the set of the platform commoners. These two sets of nodes evolve over time: new contents are created and new commoners join the platform, so that new nodes in the graph appear over time. We assume at the beginning an initial set of contents and commoners exist. Links are created over time in this graph. In particular, we describe below how links between contents and commoners and links between commoners appear over time. When a commoner posts a new content, she is the owner and a link exists a priori between her and the content. If other commoners access the content, they get connected to that content. If the content is generated by the platform owner, e.g., at bootstrap, the content is not connected to any commoner a priori. But, any content gets connected to other commoners when they access that content. If a commoner comments on a content, she will be connected to the owner of the content, since she knows that the tagged commoner made a comment on the content she posted. If a commoner replies to a comment, a new link appears between those who generated the comments.

Figure 11 depicts a sample case in order to illustrate the dynamics by which the graph evolves over time.

With the above assumptions, the graph will become denser and denser over time. At runtime, we can further account for stories which get stale over time. This can be the case for stories which have not received any comment or are not accessed anymore. In some cases they may have been removed from the platform or they may simply become not visible anymore since no activity occurs. Also, commoners can leave the platform for several reasons. Hence, links between commoners and contents are erased accordingly, and also between commoners who could know each other only through a content which has become stale; and some nodes in the graph may be removed as content and commoners come and go.

There are several standard techniques that define the

Figure 11: The evolving graph – the basic case explaining the wiring rule
Blue edges of the graph denote the formation of a neighbourhood of users a) A story (squared node) is added by a commoner (round node) b) several commons access the content and become neighbours of the author of the story when they comment on the story itself c) finally commoners interact among themselves by reacting to comments

“spreading power” of a node, which are also reflections of its connectedness and activity. For instance, the node degree, i.e., the number of a node’s neighbours, or its clustering coefficient, i.e., the number of links that connect neighbours of a node, or the node’s in-betweenness, measuring how many paths traverse the tagged node. For commonfare.net, we propose to use *coreness*. The advantage of the coreness of a node is that it connects a node to a global structural property of the graph, not a local one. Actually, it captures the fact that a node is part of an entire subgraph structure (Kitsak et al., 2010). The k -core decomposition is also computationally less expensive to calculate compared to other metrics such as in-betweenness, which is $O(n^3)$ since it is equivalent to the calculation of all-pairs shortest paths.

A node is said to have k -coreness k if it belongs to a subgraph where all nodes have at least degree k . Such a subgraph, which is unique, is denoted k -core. This will provide a relation of communication among them, which provides also information on the potential to spread information that they have.

Thus if we calculate the k -core decomposition of the graph, the group of nodes with larger coreness are those that at the time of decomposition are particularly active/effective in spreading information. In the commoner-content assemblage model adopted here, these may be commoners or particular stories (or in later releases, other digital objects).

The output of the algorithm is the identification of the k -coreness of each node. From the computational standpoint, detecting structures in graphs can be done either in centralized or decentralized manner (Montresor, De Pellegrini and Miorandi, 2013). We suggest adopting both approaches for commonfare.net, with different objectives with respect to the main project goals. The standard algorithm to compute the k -core decomposition is the one originally proposed by Batagelj and Zaversnik (2011), which we refer to henceforth as the BZ algorithm. It is a centralized node deletion algorithm which performs a deletion of vertexes (and edges incident to them) of degree less than k . It is computationally inexpensive, since it has a provable bound of $O(m)$ for a network with m edges. However, it requires random access to the whole graph, which forces typically to handle graphs of size such to be stored in the memory of servers where computations are performed. There exists a variant of this algorithm that uses external and slow memory access. The authors of BZ proposed themselves a variant which requires $O(k_{max} n)$ scans of the graph, where k_{max} is the largest coreness index of the graph.

The BZ algorithm in the original formulation is presented in Figure 12.

The basic iteration identifies the k core for $k = 1; 2; \dots; k_{max}$, where k_{max} is the maximum k -coreness of nodes of graph G . The basic iteration performs the recursive deletion of all vertices from a graph $G = (V;E)$, and all edges of degree less than k , and it leaves as final output the k core. The k -coreness of node v is also called core by Batagelj and Zaversnik (2010). The algorithm makes use of a sorted queue Q , where the first element is the node with lowest degree, and maintains (remaining) vertices sorted according to $degree[v]$ Note that

Algorithm 1: The Batagelj and Zaversnik algorithm for k -core decomposition.

```

1: Input: graph  $G = (V, E)$ 
2: Output: table  $core[v]$  contains the  $k$ -coreness of  $v \in V$ 
3: Initialize:  $Q \leftarrow V, core[v] \leftarrow degree[v]$  for all  $v \in V$ 
4: while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
5:    $v \leftarrow Q.top$ 
6:    $core[v] \leftarrow degree[v]$ 
7:   for  $u \in neighbors[v]$  do
8:     if  $degree[u] > degree[v]$  then
9:        $degree[u] \leftarrow degree[u] - 1$ 
10:    end if
11:  end for
12: end while

```

Figure 12: The BZ algorithm

the operation $Q.top$ removes the node with smaller degree in the remaining graph at each iteration.

The metric can also be applied to dynamic networks (Miorandi and De Pellegrini, 2010), e.g., an evolving graph as a social network where new nodes and edges are added over time.

We provide a pictorial example of the k -core definition in Figure 13, with respect to a sample graph. Of course, every node in the graph belongs to a 1-core, because all the graph is connected. Yellow nodes do not belong to the 2-core, so that they have coreness 1. A smaller subset of the nodes belong to the 2-core (the green nodes) but not to the 3-core, so that their coreness is 2. Finally, four blue nodes belong to the 3-core; since the 4-core is empty, their coreness is 3.

Figure 13: The k -cores of a sample graph

The k -coreness decomposition thus offers a way of recognizing and measuring the contributions made to the commonfare, within the commonfare.net platform, by individual commoners and digital objects. Since each digital object is owned by a commoner, the k -coreness of commoners could be combined with the k -coreness of the digital objects they created in order to provide a measure of their total contribution, at a given time, to the commonfare – that is, to provide a measure of their commonshare.

Taking this idea a step further, we can also envisage different ways to weight the interactions connecting commoners and digital objects. For example, ties could be weighted according to time spent on a particular page or interacting with a digital object – that way, if a commoner clicks through many pages without finding anything interesting enough to hold her attention and encourage her to read, those interactions would be valued less than interactions where a commoner has spent longer and therefore is more likely to have engaged with the content. One way of doing this would be to assign a low weight to an interaction if it lasted for less

than a specified threshold time (one second, for example). Different weights might also be assigned for different types of interaction. However, the WP3 team recommends that the system be kept as simple as possible to start with, and weighting systems only be introduced if the commoners themselves indicate that they would value this possibility.

The same idea could potentially be extended to analyse interactions in the networked assemblage constituted by the circulation among commoners of the digital currency tokens. In this case, the network nodes would be individual Social Wallets and the commoners that they are registered to, and dynamic network analysis tools such as the k -core decomposition could be applied to study how the currency tokens flow within the network, allowing for the identification of nodes that are particularly important to the fluidity of this movement.

Of course, these processes only monitor and measure interactions within the digital space, for which click data and so on are available. We should emphasise that the WP3 team recognize that substantial and important contributions to the building of the commonfare among the commonfare.net community may occur outside the platform, as individuals and groups meet and interact offline, for example through community initiatives or social gatherings, and in physical spaces such as the commonKiosks now in operation in the Netherlands pilot. However, the WP3 remit is to develop components and systems within the platform, and incorporation of extra-platform activities may need to be considered by other members of the consortium later in the project.

With this constraint in mind, the WP3 team recommend that, in the first instance, the evolving graph for the commonfare.net platform is analysed using the k -core decomposition as a way to calculate individual commoners' (and formal groups of commoners coming together in entities such as Macao, which may have a clear identity and presence on the platform) commonshares. Initially, this should be done in the background of the system, with the results only visible to members of the project team and no presentation to commoners (and thus no initial interface requirements). Since the approach to recognizing contributions to the strength of the network-assemblage we are proposing here is completely novel, such background experimentation would allow the project team to examine whether or not it is an effective way of identifying more active, cooperative commoners and digital objects that play an important role in holding the network together (possible immutable mobiles, in the language of ANT). This could be achieved through a dedicated research strand exploring the relationship between high k -coreness and the content of digital objects such as stories, and qualitative interviews with those commoners with particularly high or particularly low k -coreness.

If such research establishes reasonable correlations between k -coreness values and contributions to the strength and growth of the commonfare, then further steps could be taken to implement this contribution-recognition system in a way that is visible to commoners themselves. If not, further experiments could be conducted using alternative network measures, such as betweenness and closeness centrality or

PageRank, although these would have the disadvantage of being more computationally intensive.

The following sections suggest ways in which commonshare values, calculated using k -coreness or alternative metrics, could be used to strengthen the platform community and the common good by enhancing information diffusion, facilitating the formation of trusting relations, providing concrete rewards for contributions and detecting platform or currency misuse.

4.2.2 Using commonshare values to facilitate information diffusion

During the bootstrap phase of commonfare.net, it is important to stimulate the interest of the commoners, in order to foster the creation of contents. Ultimately, the platform should become self-sustaining, new user-generated contents would appear continuously, and in turn new interactions among commoners would be generated.

The naive strategy to foster attention of users on new contents is to indiscriminately broadcast every newly available story, by pushing a link to every user in order to provoke or make more likely their reaction. This strategy, unfortunately, does not scale well with increasing number of contents; there exists a finite budget of attention that platform users have, and this rules out the possibility that users can react to every single story (Jiang et al., 2013).

We propose to act in the bootstrap phase by posting links to new messages to the set of comments on more popular stories and a sample of them to more influential commoners, i.e., those able to interact the most with the others, both popular stories and influential commoners being identified by their k -coreness.

However, it is important to recognize the input into the design coming from potential commoners in the pilot sites. This suggests that as well as the automated pushing of stories, there could be a role for groups of individuals to select stories, initiatives or activities to feature or highlight. As one participant in the workshops described in Chapter 3 proposed,

so maybe there is a group of people, maybe a changing group of people who are like "Oh OK, we want to feature that proposal, or that debate, or that initiative at some point.

Such groups could be formed on a voluntary basis, but the k -coreness calculation could also potentially be used to invite individuals to participate more in the platform in this way.

4.2.3 Trust facilitation

So that's very important validation ... what other people think, or what the site itself thinks.

As is evident from the empirical research presented in Chapter 3, potential commoners seem keen to have representations of their own and other commoners contributions to the commonfare as an important means of establishing whether or not they share common values and so are more likely to participate in trusting interactions.

The notion of the commonshare, as captured through the k -coreness calculation described above, offers a possible way to do this. The representation of the platform as an evolving graph means that commonshares could be calculated on a regular basis – for example once each fortnight or month – and the contribution made by each commoner recognized and recorded through the k -coreness metric. Each commoner’s profile could include a representation of their commonshare history – i.e. a numerical or graphical representation of the combined k -coreness of themselves and the digital objects they own, depicted over a period of time.

Conventional reputation systems often summarize users’ standing with a multi-star scale, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Star-scale representation of user reliability/trustworthiness in conventional systems

However, a large fraction of the potential commoners interviewed during the work presented in D3.1 and participating in the workshops described in Chapter 3 of this document strongly rejected such representations. The suggestions made by participants and described in Chapter 3 included the availability of quite detailed information, including separate details on different kinds of contribution to the platform such as the number of links shared or the number of comments made. While it may be desirable to make such information available, it is likely to result in a fairly cluttered interface displaying many icons and associated numbers. Such a representation would also make it difficult to display information about a commoner’s history on commonfare in an easily digestible way. We therefore suggest a graphical representation, looking something like the graph presented in Figure 15:

Figure 15: Example of a graphical representation of the changes in metrics over time

In such a visualization, the x -axis would represent time, and the y -axis could be the commoner’s commonshare value, perhaps comparing it to the total value of the commonfare (the sum of all k -corenesses of nodes in the graph). This kind of visualization would provide a quick and relatively easily comprehensible way for a commoner to see how their own activities have changed over time, but it would also, if made public, allow other commoners to see something about their level of contribution and commitment to the platform and thus to the commonfare assemblage.

However, it is also clear from the research carried out in

WP2 and WP3 that potential commoners want access to other types of information in order to make decisions about whom to interact with. The most important of these, as described in Chapter 3 and in D3.1, appears to be the ability to see feedback in the form of text comments. While a small number of the people interviewed for D3.1 were comfortable with more conventional ratings systems, particularly when thinking of the context of transactional interactions involving goods or services, the majority expressed discomfort at the thought of having such a system incorporated in commonfare.net. Indeed, some went as far as to say that if they saw such a system, they would leave the platform and never come back. The same tendency was evident in the workshops carried out in Amsterdam and reported on in Chapter 3. We therefore suggest that no ratings system is put in place on commonfare.net, but that commoners should be able to give feedback on their interactions with others (including the quality or success of exchanges of goods, services and skills), as well as with the digital objects that those others have created or own.

Commoners could then choose whether or not to make these visible on the profile pages. Participants indicated that seeing good feedback was more important to them than seeing bad feedback, so allowing commoners to control whether or not they show feedback they have received is unlikely to have a strong negative impact on the creation or facilitation of trust.

In addition, a simple metric such as the total number of feedback comments a commoner has received could be implemented and made publicly visible, so that if a commoner has received many feedback comments but chooses not to show them, other commoners may be aware of this and reach their own contextually-informed judgements as to whether this is because the commoner in question is choosing to hide negative feedback or whether they prefer not to be judged according to such information. Such an approach would be consistent with the findings reported in Chapter 3, in which potential commoners simultaneously wanted control of what they showed, but also wanted to be able to create and see in others a coherent, values-based identity.

It is likely that if a person chooses not to show their feedback they may be less likely to be seen as suitable for immediate trusting interactions. However, it was also clear from the empirical research that potential commoners see trust as something built up over time, through a variety of interactions. If someone chooses not to make her feedback and commonshare data visible, she may receive less interactions than she otherwise would, but this is a choice she should be able to make, and she may still be able to build up a strong trust assemblage over time.

Whichever options are initially trialled, it will be important to allow the community of commoners the opportunity to negotiate among themselves what the rules of the platform regarding disclosure eventually become. This need is clear from the workshop discussion reported in Chapter 3, and is consistent with the strong desire for self-determination and control over data and privacy that has characterised all of the empirical research carried out with the pilot communities in WP2 and WP3 to date (see D3.1 in particular).

A final aspect of trust facilitation that the commonshare calculation could contribute to is the development of trust in the platform through the coherence and clarity of its values as demonstrated through its contents. As the platform evolves, it is likely to include, e.g. discussion forums; and while in the bootstrap phase members of the project team may act as moderators for content upload such as stories and forum posts, in the longer term moderators will need to be found from within the community of commoners. The commonshare metric might be used to identify those who are more committed to the platform and its goals, and who might be invited to act as moderators. This might be trialled in parallel with the system suggested by participants in the Netherlands pilot, to have newly-uploaded stories sent to a small and random selection of other commoners for approval or feedback, so that this changing group of actants produce a kind of community peer-review process that acts on the stories to approve or shape them as they are enrolled into the commonfare.net assemblage.

4.2.4 Rewarding contributions to the commonfare

Another way in which the commonshare concept could be used relates to the circulation of the digital currency. Extending our conception of the commonfare assemblage as having a value related to the density and connectedness of the network of commoners and digital objects, we could consider the possibility for commoners to “cash out” their share of that value by converting their commonshare into the platform’s digital currency(ies). This could be achieved by treating their commonshare balance as another kind of digital wallet. Another option would be for the regularly-calculated commonshares to be converted automatically into digital currency, appearing as an increase in the contents of the commoner’s digital wallet.

However, the co-design work carried out in relation to this idea to date has shown substantial ambivalence on the part of potential commoners. As described in Chapter 3, some participants in the workshops in Amsterdam were keen to have their contributions to the commonfare rewarded through some practical benefit, such as money of some kind or increased access to a pool of commonly held goods, which could be paid for in digital currency derived from either the universal income provision or a reward system. Others, however, expressed dismay at the idea of their contribution to the common good being incentivized in such a manner, and suggested that it would seriously deter them from using the platform.

Because of the timing of the various elements of the project as a whole, as noted above input into this possibility has only been obtained from freelancers in the Netherlands. Before any decisions are taken, it is essential to get more input from other groups – for example the Macao group in Milan, who are already experimenting with the use of a cryptographically-secured digital exchange token and (conditional) basic income augmented by rewards for in-house activities. The Croatian target group, who are generally younger and face different difficulties to some of the other pilot groups such as rampant corruption and clientelism (see D2.1), may be both more keen to have access

to additional channels for acquiring the digital currency, but also more suspicious of the algorithms that allocate it. A similar situation may hold true for the benefit recipients in the Netherlands. These concerns link to the question raised in the second Amsterdam workshop, about who has the power or right to issue rewards.

It is thus essential that decisions are made with participants about whether to convert commonshare to digital currency. If this option is chosen, then further decisions will need to be made, some of which reflect the outcomes of the first two sessions of the Commonpoly game – for example, whether the augmentation of a basic income should be capped and if so on what basis; etc.

4.2.5 Identifying misuse of the platform

The usage of k -cores (and hence the commonshare metric) can be extended to the detection of system misuse and collusions based on a variant of the evolving graph.

The main form of misuse we envisage that can be addressed through automated monitoring of behavioural patterns (rather than detailed analysis of content of digital objects such as stories and comments) is the manipulation of the commonshare metric, which could be done with the intention of making oneself appear more active/committed or more trustworthy, or, if linked to a reward in currency, with the intention of acquiring undeserved additional income.

At a very simple level, if k -coreness and hence commonshare are calculated based on click-through data, an individual could increase their apparent contribution to the commonfare by clicking through to many stories and comments in which they have no real interest and on which they never actually act. Such behaviour might be identified by system administrators if commoners with abnormally high k -coreness are found to have opened many resources in a very short space of time – that is, if their k -coreness value rapidly increases over a short period.

A more sophisticated form of misuse might be collusion. Some commoners may be tempted to find an agreement with others in order to stay active even without actual relevant contribution to the platform activity, e.g., by posting shallow contents or comments repeatedly with the ultimate goal to attain money. This selfish behaviour of a group of commoners would be detrimental for the commonfare since it may reduce the value of the shared stories and assign resources to individuals to an extent beyond what they deserve. Below, we describe how to use the k -core decomposition in this context in order to detect misuse events of the sort.

We can modify the dynamic graph in order to account for commoners who are actually rewarded credits for their actions on the platform. Thus, we can consider the subgraph composed by the original nodes in the evolving graph, and only retain the links between commoners that attained credits on the platform. For the sake of inspection, we may request the amount of credit attained to be above a given threshold. The rationale to do so is that, indeed, very active commoners will likely be connected to each other since they will comment and react to contents on the platform.

However, we do not expect to see very active commoners to be necessarily connected preferentially among themselves, since it means that they tend to comment on each other's contents or to each other's comments, which may be a symptom of collusion.

For instance, the type of event which would represent an anomaly could be a triplet of commoners who are connected to each other and continuously comment on each other's contents and posts. We can imagine three individuals, say Bob, Alice and Tom. They know that they will be rewarded a certain credit based on their activity on commonfare.net. If credits/rewards are based on a commoner's commonshare, they increase with number of contents they post and the number of comments they post and receive, thus increasing the density of the graph and the connectedness of both themselves and the digital objects they own/create. Hence, Alice proposes to Bob and Tom the following scheme: she will post a new content on the platform, and both Bob and Tom will react with comments, in the form of a thread, involving the three of them, and maybe some other random platform user, not colluding with them, but sincerely interested in the posted content. Bob and Tom will also post a digital object each (perhaps in the form of a new story or a discussion forum item), and they will receive comments from the other two, respectively. For the colluding three, the actual information or advice conveyed in the digital object is irrelevant and could be of little or no value to others. For example, they could repeat content or post stories that have no connection to the experiences and activities of those experiencing financial and employment precarity; and it is conceivable that bots could be created to continuously comment on each other's stories without any actual interaction or involvement. Hence, they will be able to increase their commonshare without necessarily contributing to the increased strength and value of the commonfare. In the case of three colluding individuals, it will be sufficient to identify triangles of those who interact preferentially among themselves, i.e., cliques of order 3.

For larger collusions, we should not expect *a priori* users to interact within cliques of given order $n > 3$, and more general relations for colluders may be involved. In fact, the advantage they may obtain is the higher, the larger the number of colluders they interact with. But, some of them may collude only with a fraction of the others. If some collusion occurs, however, we expect to witness the formation of subgraphs where each node received a relatively larger credit than a randomly sampled node, and it has several neighbours who do the same. This maybe so simply because they colluded in order to rank higher each other, e.g., as in the previous example, being very active on each other comments or contents.

Thus, the proposed detection process would be described by the following procedure:

- ▶ Define a reward threshold h
- ▶ Select the subset V_R of users receiving larger reward than h
- ▶ Build the evolving graph considering links only among users who are in V

- ▶ Determine at each point in time the coreness k of the elements of V_R
- ▶ If $k > 3$ for some users, mark the users as potential colluders

Of course, the presence of a larger k -core may be indicating that some of large groups of colluders is present on the platform, and this may trigger direct intervention, e.g., by the platform's administrators, in order to directly verify the good faith of the actions performed on the platform.

The detection strategies proposed above are meant to identify potential misbehaviour and misuse of the system. As discussed in the previous section, a primary concern is associated with the trust facilitation, and especially possible reward mechanisms if it is converted (or convertible) into the digital currency. However, platform misuse is a general concern in online social networks and may include other undesirable behaviours, such as offensive contents or online bullying. This has been raised by the Croatian pilot partners in particular, because of the current popularity of far right views in Croatia, and visceral ethnic divisions. In general such behaviours may involve several events depending on users' will and which cannot be excluded at design time. A set of possible concrete actions to be implemented by the platform administrators are sketched below.

We observe that deviant behaviours of single individuals are common in social networks. Usually, they can be coped with by using careful monitoring and reporting. The commonfare.net platform could be equipped with simple deterrents, for example empowering commoners to judge and report on inappropriate content or activities by providing online reporting tools. These are typically provided in the form of flags for inappropriate content (implemented via clickable flag icons associated with each digital content object), emails to the platform administrator or standard online forms for abuse reporting.

Of course, such systems rely on platform administration of some sort, which is an issue that needs to be addressed in the longer term sustainability of commonfare.net. The suggestions made by the participants in the workshop on trust, contribution and reward described in Chapter 3 may be relevant in this respect. In that workshop, the idea of a small and changing group of commoners taking on the role of "editors" or "peer reviewers" who selected stories and initiatives that should be featured (or highlighted) by the platform. The fact that potential commoners are themselves suggesting cooperative roles that contribute to the administration of the platform provides a hopeful indication that the cooperative, communal ethos of commonfare.net will encourage others to participate in other administrative tasks, for example following up on reports of abusive comments or inappropriate content. Because of the nature of the involvement of potential participants through the pilots partners, it may be that such commoners, willing to take on a more active role in contributing to site administration, can be identified through personal contact initially. Once the platform has established itself and the community of commoners starts to grow beyond those brought in by the pilot partners, it may be desirable to issue calls on the platform for volunteers to join a list of

potential administrators and then automate a rotation of duties over some period of time, to be negotiated among the volunteering commoners themselves.

In the case of non-meaningful connections and collusion, though, these activities undermine the core aim of the contribution-recognition and potential reward mechanisms, so that the situation is critical at the design level. They may involve several users and their aggregated behaviour thus may cause larger scale effects onto the platform. For instance, we could face an imbalance contribution-recognition and/or reward assignment across the platform, which ultimately would end with favouring certain groups to the detriment of the remaining commoners. In the unlikely extreme cases of large scale misbehaviours, the primary goal will be to safeguard the values and wealth of the community as a whole, which might mean administrators would need to consider, for example, removing commonshare values, freezing the circulation of the digital coin or implementing other contingency plans in order to react to collusion effects.

In the more likely event of smaller, localized colluding groups, inspection and discussion with the users would be the preferred mean of intervention. In fact, local communities may be built within the commonfare.net structure, because of, e.g., geographical localization, and certain groups of commoners may be naturally organized in specific clusters corresponding to formal or informal groups of commoners with shared interests or initiatives. In those cases, “collusions” may be a simple effect of localization, with no harmful intent.

In this respect, direct inspection of the quality and the dynamics of the posted contents would be sufficient to rule out the presence of anomalies.

4.2.6 Summary of integrated dynamic network analysis and contribution, trust facilitation and reward proposals

In this section, we have outlined a novel approach to measuring the contribution/activity of commoners to the commonfare.net platform, to take the place of a

more conventional, individually-focused and acquisitive reputation system. We have also made some suggestions about how this commonshare metric might be used in facilitating information diffusion, the establishment of trust, a possible reward system and misuse detection.

However, we are aware that, as an entirely novel approach, there may be unforeseen problems and consequences. We therefore strongly recommend that initial experiments are conducted in the background of the platform development, rather than made immediately visible on the platform interface. One possibility is that the proposed approach is too simple and too blunt a metric, unable to distinguish, for example, between constructive cooperation within groups and less well-intentioned collusion. It will be essential for the project consortium to conduct research to determine whether high commonshare values, as calculated through the k -core decomposition, actually correspond to behaviours and participations that are actually valued by commoners.

We are also sensitive to the concerns expressed by some potential commoners about anything that could give the platform a commercial, competitive or individualistic appearance – or anything that appeared to be imposed from the top down – and so potentially undermine the creation of common, cooperative and mutualistic approaches.

For these reasons, we urge that potential commoners are more widely included in co-design activities that test the utility of our suggestions and their congruence with the values of the commonfare.net community. We also suggest that provision be made within the platform, for example through dedicated wikis or discussion forums, to allow ongoing discussion and negotiation among commoners of the platform's norms and rules.

5. SUMMARY

This document presented the final suggestions and recommendations arising from WP3.

WP3's remit included desk-top and empirical research and development work towards the creation of components/systems on the commonfare.net platform that would:

- ▶ Allow for the implementation of complementary, digital currencies in the form of cryptographically-secured digital exchange tokens
- ▶ Facilitate information diffusion
- ▶ Facilitate the formation of trusting relationships; and hence
- ▶ Contribute to the long-term sustainability and growth of the platform, and so to the creation or facilitation of a commonfare approach to welfare provision in Europe.

In chapter 2, we presented an overview of the commonfare concept and the possibilities for the platform. We also presented a novel conceptualization of the platform as an assemblage of users (commoners) and digital objects or resources (such as stories and profiles) which underpinned the development of many of the ideas subsequently presented in Chapter 4.

In Chapter 3, we summarized the results of earlier empirical research, already published in D2.1 and D3.1 of particular relevance to WP3. We also presented new findings from subsequent work. We noted that key issues of relevance to WP3 include:

- ▶ A widespread desire to feel part of a community with shared values, especially one which cooperates and acts in a mutualistic way to increase the quality of life of the many.
- ▶ Widespread concern over privacy and data control issues, and a concomitant mistrust of technical corporations and platforms such as Google and Facebook.
- ▶ New forms of rather fragmented solidarity that may result in overly-segregated group formation and hence obstacles to the diffusion of knowledge and good practice.
- ▶ A strong desire for self-determination, autonomy, and freedom from conditionalities imposed by the State,

non-governmental authorities such as NGOs, and capitalist entities such as employers and big businesses.

- ▶ A perception that trust in the platform would be as or even more important than trust in the individuals a commoner might potentially interact with.
- ▶ The increasing prevalence and hidden impact of personal indebtedness.
- ▶ Willingness to experiment with complementary (digital) currencies.
- ▶ Interest in currency systems that include an unconditional basic income, and that exclude loans at interest and speculation.
- ▶ Ambivalence or contradictory views about whether contributions to the common good should be rewarded, but a general desire that they should be recognized and visible to others.

These findings have important implications for the design of the platform, including but not limited to the components/systems described in Chapter 4.

Chapter 4 made concrete proposals for components/systems on the commonfare.net platform within the remit of WP3.

Section 4.1 dealt specifically with three alternatives for implementing one or more digital currencies in the form of cryptographically-secured digital exchange tokens.

The first of these options was a currency system based on the digital currency for the cooperative movement, Faircoin2. We noted that Faircoin aligns well with the commonfare project in terms of ethics and ethos, but that it has some potential disadvantages relating to scalability and hence long-term sustainability of the platform, especially beyond the life of the formal PIE News project.

The second option considered was use of the Yetta Protocol and associated smart contracts, and the use of the Yetta Token in the platform. This has the advantage of good potential for scalability and long-term sustainability, because it introduces a mechanism for the influx of additional financial capital into commonfare.net (and hence to the community of commoners) on a long-term, continuous basis. However, it does so on the basis of prosocial spending and philanthropic

investment, something which could bring its own risks for platform sustainability. For example, if the expected returns are not high, this could disincentivize further investments into the system, something which the project partners and platform would have no control over.

The third option presented in Section 4.1 was a dual complementary currency system introducing both the Yetta Token (as described in the second option) and a site-specific coin. This site-specific coin would have the advantages of being closed, autonomous and independent, and could function as an exchange token within the commoner community. However, it would not provide much advantage in terms of actual debt relief or income generation for use in non-commonfare.net related contexts – hence the suggestion of maintaining a parallel currency system using the Yetta Token.

Section 4.2 focused on integrating network dynamics analysis and systems for the facilitation of trust, the recognition of constructive contributions towards the commonfare, and detection of (and subsequent action on) platform misuse. Building on the notion of commonfare.net as an assemblage described in Chapter 2, we proposed using network dynamics metrics to calculate the contribution individual actants in the network (both commoners and digital resources) made to the strength of the commonfare

in any given period. We proposed calling the aggregate contribution of a commoner and the digital resources she owns her commonshare. We then made a series of suggestions for how the commonshare value might be used to enhance the strength, growth and sustainability of the platform. Because this is a novel approach, we strongly suggest that it first be trialled through experiments on the platform's trace data carried out in the background, with no representation or visibility on the platform interface. We also noted that final decisions regarding some of the norms and rules on the platform should be negotiated within the commoner community, rather than imposed from the level of the project consortium. To this end, we urged more participatory co-design work around these kind of components and systems, together with dedicated space on the commonfare.net platform (perhaps in the form of a wiki or discussion forum) in which commoners can discuss and reach consensus.

The proposals sketched out above and laid out in more detail in the main body of this document are complex and ambitious. It is now up to the project consortium to decide which of them it wants to try out, and what to prioritize in terms of development time and resources.

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